

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
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processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Product analysis and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, Product analysis and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments; Journal of
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Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com, s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 5 March 2026.

Keynote

A merchandising report of aroma encapsulated inner garments in 2015-2016 was reported to satisfy the
funding authority of higher education and research. A merchandising of PhD research outcome was
continued, overviewed, and assessed the comments of customers and relevant retailers of textile and
fashion. It was a nine months duration full-time research project of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar
Hossain. The nine-month salary compensation was 27,00,000BDT for merchandising, founding, branding,
running a new project, extra hours contributions, and research services. A short summary of research
outcomes, research project billing, and financial record were also officially reported to University of
Calcutta to satisfy PhD research, academic practice, PhD funding, PhD salary, PhD project, and 'PhD¹
compensation award' of author in 2015-2017 [1-4] [1, 2, 4, 5] [5-12] [13] [3] [14, 15] [16] [2, 4, 12, 17].

1 Discussion

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-sold and self-supplied the cosmetic textiles in the
name of ladies inner garments in the name of 'fragrance finished bra' in 2016. Professor Dr. Engr.
Md. Anowar Hossain got and recorded a lot of positive comments from local retailers in
Bangladeshi supermarkets at Dhaka and Chittagong. He self-visited around 100 supermarkets in
Dhaka City and Chittagong City in Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also
self-collected and self-reviewed around 500 customer's overviews at his self-show room at Rajuk
Trade Center Shopping Mall, Regency Hotel Building, Nikunja-2, Khilkhet, Dhaka-1229,
Bangladesh[18]. Many local businessmen in garments show room commented positively about the
cosmetic textiles in 2016 who told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in different ways
in different review meetings, "your product is the new product in Bangladeshi markets in terms of
fragrance-finished inner garments, we didn't get, we didn't sell such type of product in previous
time; although we also purchased product from India." Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
also self-visited K-mart in Australia in 2020-2022. K-Mart was selling different Bangladeshi
products in Melbourne, Australia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also self-funded and

self-visited different local shops in Melbourne. But Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't see any product of cosmetic textiles, any product of cosmetic finished inner garments in Melbourne. So, there is scope to develop the technology of technical textiles in terms of cosmetic and medicinal properties of textiles. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also extended his relevant research in relevant material design for aroma encapsulated inner garments for medical textiles, and color engineering. Materials of natural source were prioritized due to eco-friendly method design and human-friendly product design [1-4] [1, 2, 4, 5] [5-12] [13] [3] [14, 15] [16] [2, 4, 17].

Figure 1. Office of PhD research of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain on 'cosmetic textiles' at Dhaka, Bangladesh; funded by chief executive officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion.

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2 A short summary and evidence of field trialing costs of cosmetic textiles of MTech thesis and/or MPhil/PhD¹ thesis on “simultaneous dyeing and fragrance finishing of cotton fabric” at University of Calcutta, India

Figure 1, a field trialing of cosmetic textiles at University of Calcutta, India marketed and branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion; sole authored and sole funded by Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. The thesis was also officially registered and archived a printed copy and a digital copy at University Grants Commission of Bangladesh since 2017[12]. Every self-funded research should keep a record of the expenses for claiming his research and development costs. Every research is a contribution to the global community under the representation of university in academia and philosophia. What should be the judicial benefit of an author? Who paid money to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain? No government paid money to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. No university paid money to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India can/should manage a recognition of certificate and/or ‘PhD¹ compensation award’ to the author.

Date: 01/03/26
 Office Expenditure, January: 2026

Office Salary : 50,000₹
 Office Advance : 17,000₹
 Furniture : 29490₹
 Conveyance : 3650₹
 Lunch : 2134₹
 Entertainment : 500₹
 Office rent : 2000₹
 Office Stationery : 3604₹
 Sample purchasing : 2690₹
 Purchasing poly : 100₹
 Office Nameplate : 1000₹
 Mobile Bill : 2200₹
 Internet Bill : 500₹
 Surfactant : 900₹
 Hanger : 200₹
 Purchasing Tray & glam for tea : 390
 Trade Fair Entry Ticket : 30
 Biza Production : 66360₹
 Total → 1,18,388₹ + 66,360₹
 = 184,748₹

Approved By
 01.03.2026
 Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Engagement Officer & Researcher
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Dhaka-1212

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Bill

Date: 03/03/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : office Advance

Description :

Advance to Hotel owner → 17000₹
 (02 month rent)

Approved
 &
 Received By

 03/03/16

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বিস্মিত্তাহির রাহমানির রাহিম

বিঃস্মিত্তাহির রাহমানির রাহিম

ক্যাশ মেমো ম্যানেজারঃ ০১৭৭১-৯৩০১১৩

বিক্রমপুর ফার্ণিচার
Bikrampur Furniture

এখানে সকল প্রকার ফার্ণিচার সামগ্রী পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 কারখানা : ৫০৭/৩, ৫২, ময়নারবাগ, হোসেন মার্কেট, উত্তর বাডডা, ঢাকা-১২১২
 পো-কম : রোড # ১৪, প্লট # ১/সি, কিলেক্ট, দিহু-২, (সোটাস কামাল টাওয়ারের পাশে), ঢাকা-১২২১।
 ফোনঃ- ০১৮১৮-৪১৩১৭৪, ০১৬৭৭-১৫১৪৮৫

নং **626** তারিখ **২৭/০২/২০২৫**

নাম	জোয়া মামু হোসেন			ক্রতার মোবা	
ঠিকানা	রোড #				

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
১	৫ ½ জোয়া মামু (১০টি) + ১৫২০ (১০টি)	৩৮		
২	২০০ (৬০০) কাইল	১৮		
৩	সেটি মামু (৬০টি)	২৮	২৪৬০০	৩৪৬০০
				মোট- ২৪৬০০
				অগ্রিম- ৫
				বাকী-

০২/০১/২০২৫
 Approved BB
 ০১/০১/২৬

টাকা কথায়ঃ

নিজে নামাজ পড়ুন, অন্যকে নামাজ পড়তে উৎসাহিত করুন।
 বিঃদ্রঃ বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না

ক্রতার স্বাক্ষর বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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ক্যাশ মেমো

মোবা : ০১৯১৩-১৭২৭৭০
: ০১৯১৩-১৭২৭৭০

মিনহাজ বেডিং স্টোর MINHAJ BEDDING STORE

প্রোঃ মোঃ মিজান মিয়া

এখানে উন্নতমানের লেপ, তোষক, জাজিম, মশরী, পর্দা, বালিশের কভার, লেপের কভার বিছানার চাদর, ফোম কভার, কুশন ইত্যাদি কাজ সুদক্ষ কারিগর দ্বারা তৈরী ও বিক্রয় করা হয় এবং পুরাতন কাজ রিপিংয়ারিং করা হয়।

দোকান নং-২, রোড নং-১২, খিলক্ষেত টানপাড়া, নিকুঞ্জ, ঢাকা-১২২৯

নং- 74

তারিখ ২০ ২০ ২৬

নাম ০১৭৩২০৮১১০৭

ডেলিঃ তারিখ ২০ ২০ ২৬

ঠিকানা

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
	<p>Approved By 02/03/26 Md. Anowar Hossain Professor & Research Consultant</p>			২০০০
			মোট-	২০০০
			অগ্রীম-	৫০০
			বাকী-	১৫০০

বিঃ দ্রঃ ২১ দিনের মধ্যে মাল ডেলিভারী নিতে হবে। ২১ দিন পরে মালের কোন ক্ষতি/নষ্ট হলে কর্তৃপক্ষ দায়ী থাকিবে না। বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না।

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Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25: School of Fashion
and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1

বিস্মিল্লাহির রাহমানির রাহিম
ক্যাশ মেমো মানোজারঃ ০১৭৭১-৯৩০১১৩

বিক্রমপুর ফার্নিচার
Bikrampur Furniture

এখানে সকল প্রকার ফার্নিচার সামগ্রী পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 কারখানা : ৫০৭/৩.৫২, ময়নারবাগ, হোসেন মার্কেট, উত্তর বাজড়া, ঢাকা-১২১২
 পৌ-ক্রম : রোড # ১৪, গুট # ১/সি, বিনকেত, নিবৃষ্-২, (সেটাস কামাল টাওয়ারের পাশে), ঢাকা-১২২৯।
 ফোনঃ- ০১৮১৮-৪১৩১৭৪, ০১৬৭৭-১৫১৪৮৫

নং **627** তারিখ **০১/০২/২০২৬**

নাম **আব্দুল্লাহ এম** জেতার মোবা

ঠিকানা

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
০১	২'x৬' বর্ড	১৭	২৪০০/	২৪০০/
				মোট- ২৪০০/০০
				অর্থম- ৫
				বাকী-

02/02/2026
 Approved By
 01/02/26

টাকা কথায় :

নিজে নাগাজ পড়ুন, অন্যকে নাগাজ পড়তে উৎসাহিত করুন।

বিঃ দ্রঃ বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না

ক্রোতার স্বাক্ষর বিক্রোতার স্বাক্ষর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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বাংলা ————— ইংরেজি

হাওলাদার ফার্নিচার

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All Kinds of Latest T.V. Trolley, Chair, Coat Hanger And Office Furniture Retailer & Supplier

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সূত্র : তারিখ : ৩-২-১৬

১) *কম্পিউটার ২৫ টি/খাটাই = ২৫ = ৩৪০০৬*

Approved By

 02/02/16

৩৪০০৬

 1/2/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
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Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
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শাহজাদপুর আব্দুল মান্নান রাস্তায়

ক্যাশ মেমো
বিক্রয় কেন্দ্র

রাফিক এন্ড ব্রাদার্স-৩
RAFIQUE & BROTHERS
A House of Quality (PVC) Plastic & Fibre Door

সব্বিয়ার গ্রাসের দরজা, ডোরার টেবিল, চেইটিন, প্রেসসিট, শাওয়ার ট্রে, প্রাটিক (PVC) সিটের দরজা
 কাঠের দরজা, স্টেকট, গাঙ্গী পানির ট্যাকে এবং গৃহশোভা সামগ্ৰী প্রস্তুতকারক বিক্রেতা ও সরবরাহকারী।
 বাড়ী # ১, বাসা ৪ ১৭, নিকুল-২, জরসাহারা, ঢাকা-১২২৯।
 ফোন হেড অফিসঃ ৯১২৪০১৪, ৯১১২৩৫৫ শো-রুমঃ ০১৭৪৯-৫১৭৮১৬

নং- **349** চালান নং- তারিখঃ **2/2/20**

নামঃ
 ঠিকানাঃ

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	দর	টাকা
১	২০০০	২০	২০
২	২০০০	৫০	৫০
৩	২০০০	৫০	৫০
		বাকী-	

টাকা (কম্বায়)ঃ
 শর্তবন্দীঃ

* মোট মূল্যের কমপক্ষে ৫০% অগ্রিম এবং অবশিষ্ট মূল্য সরবরাহের সময় প্রদান করতে হবে। *সাধারণভাবে
 সরবরাহের তারিখ আন্তরিকভাবে ঠিক রাখা হবে। কিন্তু দুর্ঘটনা জনিত কারণে যদি সরবরাহের তারিখ পিছিয়ে যায় তার
 জন্য কোন ধরনের ক্ষতিপূরণ দাবী করতে পারবে না। *ক্রয় আদেশ পাওয়ার অব্যাহতি পূর্বে প্রস্তুতকরণ
 প্রক্রিয়া শুরু হবে। কাজেই ক্রয় আদেশ প্রদানের পর ক্রয় আদেশ ফরমে কোন রূপ পরিবর্তন আনা যাবে না।

ক্রয়তার স্বাক্ষর **বিঃ দ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না।** **পক্ষে- রাফিক এন্ড ব্রাদার্স**

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Date: 01/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Office Searching

Description:

Mohakhali to Nikunja → 10₳

Nikunja to Mohakhali → 45₳

(By Bus & Rickshaw)

Total → 55₳

Approved

&

Received By

01/01/16

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 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill Date: 01/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chaitman

Purpose: office searching at Mohakhali & Nikunja

Description :

Lunch Bill → 150f

Total → 150f

Approved
&
Received By
[Signature]
01/01/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 01/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Official Meeting at Modina Restaurant
with garments producers.

Description:

Coffee & light food → 500f

Approved
&
Received By
[Signature]
01/01/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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Conveyance Bill

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Date : 05/01/16

Post : Chairman

Purpose : Office searching at Nikunja

Description :

Tongi office to Nikunja → 35₹
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Nikunja to Tongi office → 25₹

Total → 60₹

Approved
 &
 Received By

Anowar
 05/01/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Module 01, 25 Dawson Street
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Lunch Bill

Date: 05/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: office searching at Nikunja

Description:

Approved
&
Received By

[Signature]
05/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Mobile: 01732231104
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
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 Former Assisist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assisist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
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 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assisist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Date: 06/01/2016

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : Office furniture purchasing

Description :

Tongi office to Nikunja → 35f
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Nikunja to Tongi office → 35f

Total → 70f

Approved

&

Received By

[Signature]

06/01/15

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

[Faint stamp]

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 06/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Office furniture Purchasing

Description:

Lunch Bill

150/-

Approved

&

Received By

A. H.

06/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Chairman
Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
Mobile: 01732681104
Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh);
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing &
 process, color engg), applied law & criminology
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 Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court;
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
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 Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Date: 07/01/16

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Visiting Garments factory at Salna,
 Joydevpur

Description:

Tongi office to Salna → 30f
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Salna to Tongi Office → 30f

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 07/01/16

Engr M. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Textile, Color & Material Research Centre
 RMIT University
 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
 engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date : 07/01/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : Visiting Garments factory at Salna, Joydevpur.

Description :

Approved
&
Received By
A. Hossain
07/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Mobile: 01722931104
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Date: 08/01/16

Post: chairman

Purpose: visiting Garments factory

Description :

Tongi office to Mirpur-01 → 90f
(By Bus & Rickshaw)

Mirpur-01 to Tongi office → 90f

Total → 180f

Approved and

Received By

08/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
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 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Date: 08/01/16

Post: chairman

Purpose: visiting Garments factory

Description:

Approved and

Received By

[Signature]
08/01/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh);
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 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
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 Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
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 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
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 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

**Office Rent
 January - 2016**

Date: 08/01/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : chairman

Description :

Office rent, Gazipur, Tongi → 2000₹

Approved By

[Signature]
 08/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Mobile: 01712681104
 Email: engr.an@unghwando.com

Received By

[Signature]
 08/01/16
 01715550402

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
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Conveyance Bill

Date: 09/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Visiting Buying house at Uttara

Description:

Tongi office to Uttara buying → 40f
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Uttara to Tongi office → 40f

|
 Total → 80f

Approved
&

Received By

[Signature]
 09/01/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
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 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 09/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Visiting Buying house at Uttara.

Description:

Lunch Bill → 150₳

Total → 150₳

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 09/01/16

Engr Md. Anowar Hossain
 [Signature]
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 M.I.T. Textile & Fashion
 [Signature]

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
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Conveyance Bill

Date: 10/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: office pad & visiting card making

Description:

Tongi office to khilkhet → 25f
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

khilkhet to Tongi office → 25f

|
 Total → 50f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 10/01/16

Engr Md. Anowar Hossain
 Bangladesh Textile Engineering Institute
 Dhaka

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
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 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
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Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 10/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Office pad & visiting card making

Description:

**Approved
&
Received By**

Anowar
10/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Mobile: 017229931104
 Email: anowar@rmit.edu.au

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
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 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 10/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Purchasing office seal (Chairman)

Description:

Office Seal —————→ 70f

Stamp pad —————→ 50f

Total → 120f

Approved
&

Received By

[Signature]
10/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 10/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Description:

- 1) Preparing office pad → 1200f
- 2) Making visiting card → 400f

Approved By

 10/03/16

~~Approved~~
 Received By
 01931118111
 MD ALAM G/R

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Defence & Law Research Centre
 RMIT University
 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

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Bill

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Date: 11/03/16

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Sample Purchasing

Description:

1. Sample purchasing from Nikunja → 600f
(1 pc)
2. Sample purchasing from Gazipur → 250f
(02 pcs)
3. Sample purchasing from Board Bazar → 200f
(02 pcs)

Total → 1050f

Approved
&
Received By

Anowar
11/03/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Chairman
Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
Mobile: 01732581104
Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

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Conveyance Bill

Date: 11/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Market research & sample purchasing

Description:

- Tongi office to Nikunja → 15f
- Nikunja to Boatd Bazar → 20f
- Boatd Bazar to Gazipur chowrasta → 10f

Total → 55f

Approved
&
Received By

Anowar
11/01/16

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Lunch Bill

Date: 11/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Inquiry about office furniture purchasing

Description:

Lunch Bill → 150f

Total → 150f

Approved
&
Received By

[Signature]
11/01/16

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নিসমিত্তাহির রাহমানির রাহিম
ক্যাশ মেমো
লাদেন সুতা ঘর
শ্রোঃ মোঃ সাহাব উদ্দিন

মোবাইল : ০১৭৩২-৫৪০০২৮, ০১৭৩০-৯৩৭৩৫০
 এখানে সকল প্রকার গার্মেন্টস, টেইলারিং এ্যাম্ব্রয়ডারী সহ যাবতীয়
 সুইং সুতা ও দেশী-বিদেশী লেইজ সুলভ মূল্যে বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 কোনাবাড়ী নিউ মার্কেট, দোকান নং ডি-৫, কোনাবাড়ী, গাজীপুর।

নং **6766** তারিখ **১২/১/১৬**

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
০১	সুতা	২ kg	১০০০	২০০০
০২				
০৩				
০৪				
০৫				
০৬				
০৭				
০৮				
০৯				
১০				
১১				
১২				
১৩				
১৪				
১৫				
	ধন্যবাদ আবার আসবেন।		মোট	২০০০

টাকা (কথায়) **২০০০**
 ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর বিঃ দ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল ফেরৎ লওয়া হয় না।

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ক্যাল মেমো

মোবাইল : ০১৯২০-২২০৪০১

সাদিয়া হোসিয়ারী গার্মেন্ট

গোঃ মোঃ আলমগীর হোসেন

এখানে সকল প্রকার রেডিমেট গার্মেন্টস পোশাক পাইকারী বিক্রয় করা হয়।

নতুন বাজার, কোনাবাড়ী, গাজীপুর।

নং-

1854

তারিখ

২২/৩/১৯

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
১	সারা ৩২/৩৬	১	৩৫৫	৩৫৫
২	-	১	৬০০	৬০০
৩	-	১	২৫০	২৫০
৪	৩৬/৪০	১	৬০০	৬০০
৫	চিকি ৩৬/৪০	১	৪০০	৪০০
৬	৩২/৩৬	১	২৯০	২৯০
৭	-	২৫৫	২৫০	২৫০
৮				২২৪০
৯				
১০				
১১				
১২				
১৩				
১৪				
১৫				
মোট =				

১২/০১/১৬
ক্রোতার স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রিত মাল কেবল নেওয়া হয়ে না।

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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Conveyance Bill

Date: 12/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Purchasing sample from Konabari

Description:

Tongi office to Konabari → 35₹
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)
 Konabari to Tongi office → 40₹

↓
 Total → 75₹

Approved
 &
 Received By

[Signature]
 12/03/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Material
 Textile

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Lunch Bill

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Date: 12/01/16

Post: chairman

Purpose: Purchasing sample from Konabari

Description:

Lunch Bill → 150₹

Total → 150₹

Approved

&

Received By

12/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

Chairman
Mobile: +8801788396264

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 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
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Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Date: 13/03/16

Bill

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Description:

Office Name plate → 300f

Total → 300f

Approved By
 [Signature]
 13/03/16

Received By
 [Signature]
 13/03/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Date: 13/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: office Nameplate making

Description :

Tongi office to khilkhet → 25f
(By Bus & Rickshaw)

khilkhet to Tongi office → 25f

Approved
&
Received By

13/01/16

Total → 50f

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill Date: 13/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Making office name plate

Description:

Approved
 &
 Received By

 13/02/16

Dr. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

Date: 13/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Office stationery purchasing

Description:

A4 Size papers → 20₳

Pen refill → 30₳

Total → 50

Approved
&
Received By

[Signature]
13/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

Chairman

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Mobila Bill

Date: 14/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Official Mobila Bill

Description:

Approved
&
Received By

[Signature]
14/03/16

[Faint purple stamp]

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Internet Bill

Date: 14/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Official Internet Browning

Description:

Grameen phone internet → 300f

Approved

&

Received By

[Signature]

14/01/16

Engr M. Anowar Hossain

[Faint stamp]

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh);
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 14/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Budget purchasing for office

Description:

Budget price → 800f

Budget netting charge
& Tape purchasing → 100f

Total → 900f

Approved
&
Received By

[Signature]
14/03/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Conveyance Bill

Date: 14/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: office pad & visiting card receiving
 Business purchasing

Description:

Tongi office to Nikunja → 35₹
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Nikunja to Tongi office → 35₹

Total = 70₹

Approved
 &
 Received By

 14/01/16

Faint, illegible text at the bottom of the page.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 14/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

**Purpose: office pad & visiting card receiving
 Buttern purchasing**

Description:

**Approved
 &
 Received By**

14/01/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Lunch Bill

Date: 16/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to factory, Salna.

Description:

Lunch Bill → 150f

Approved
&
Received By

Abul
16/01/16

Faint, illegible handwritten notes or stamps.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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Conveyance Bill

Date: 16/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to factory, Salna.

Description:

Tongi office to salna → 30₹
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Salna to Tongi office → 30₹

Total → 60₹

Approved
&
Received By

[Signature]
16/01/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 17/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Bapari Garments & Impertial dyeing & finishing .

Description :

Approved
 &
 Received By
[Signature]
 17/01/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
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 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶
 Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
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 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
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 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill Date: 17/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Bapari Garments & Imperial
 dyeing & finishing.

Description:

Tongi office to Bapari Garments → 80₹
 (Narayangong)

Bapari Garments to Tongi Office → 80₹
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

|
 Total → 160₹

Approved
 &
 Received By

 17/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bapari Garments & Imperial
 Dyeing & Finishing
 Narayangong, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Conveyance Bill

Date: 18/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Noyamati Narayanganj

Description:

Tongi office to Noyamati → 140₳
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Noyamati to Tongi office → 120₳
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Approved
 &
 Received By

(Signature)
 18/01/16

Engr Md. Anowar Hossain
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK),
 PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia),
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 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 18/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to Noyamati, Nattaganong.

Description:

Lunch Bill → 150₹

Approved & Received By

[Signature]
18/01/16

Total → 150₹

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

Date: 18/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to Noyamati, Narayanganj.

Description:

Approved
&
Received By

A. Hossain
18/01/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill Date: 19/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Market research at Tongi Zone

Description:

Approved
&
Received By

(Signature)
19/03/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Market Research Group
 Engr Md Anowar Hossain

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
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Bill

Date: 20/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Brca Production

Description:

Brca → $756 \times 60 = 45360\text{f}$

Box → $4200 \times 5 = 21000\text{f}$

Total → 66360f

Approved

&

Received By

20/03/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 21/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to Salna, Gazipur for sample

Description:

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 21/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Conveyance Bill

Date: 21/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Salna, Gazipur for sample

Description:

Tongi office to Salna → 30₳
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Salna to Tongi office → 30₳

Approved
&
Received By

Anowar
21/01/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain

(Faint signature and stamp)

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Date: 23/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman

Purpose: Enquiry about sewing m/c price

Description:

Tongi office to Abdullahpur, Tongi → 20₳
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Abdullahpur to Tongi office → 15₳

Total → 35₳

Approved
 &
 Received By
 A.H.
 23/01/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Lunch Bill

Date : 23/01/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : chairman

Purpose : Inquiry about sewing m/c price

Description :

Lunch Bill → 150f

Approved
&

Received By

23/01/16

Faint handwritten notes and stamps at the bottom of the page.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³
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 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
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Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Tea Bill

Date: 23/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Enquiry about sewing m/c purchasing

Description:

Approved
&
Received By

(Signature)
23/01/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Member, ITC-UNCTAD/WTO
 School of Fashion and Textiles

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

01

Bill

Date: 23/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: stationery purchasing

Description:

A4 size paper → 10₳

Pen refill → 20₳

Total → 30₳

Approved
&
Received By

23/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Chairman
Barrister (Dr.)
Mobile: 01788396264
Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
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Bill Date: 23/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Purchasing sample
 Description:

Lingerie purchasing from market → 500f

Total → 500f

Approved
 &
 Received By
 Anowar
 23/01/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
 23/01/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

Date: 25/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Trade fair entry ticket.

Description:

Trade fair entry ticket → 30f

Approved
&
Received By

[Signature]
25/01/16

Total → 30f

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Date: 25/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to International Trade Fair-16

Description:

Tongi office to Agargaon → 50₳
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Agargaon to Tongi office → 50₳

Approved
&
Received By

(Signature)
25/03/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 RMIT University
 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 25/03/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : Going to International trade fair-16.

Description :

Lunch Bill → 150₳

Total → 150₳

Approved
&
Received By

Anowar
25/03/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Chairman
Bangladesh Textile Mills Association
Member - 01, Dhaka-1104
e-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Date: 25/03/16

Bill

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman

Purpose: Purchasing Tray & glam for Tea

Description:

Glam - 02 per → 200₳
 Tray - 01 per → 170₳
 Stickers for office decoration → 20₳

Total → 390₳

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 25/03/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Mobile: 01788396264
 Email: engr.anowar@yaho.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

Date: 25/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Purchasing Hanger

Description:

Four Headed Hanger → ২০০₳
 (০৩ পিস)
 For sample showing

Approved

&

Received By

(Signature)

25/03/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Museum © 1712/2014-2016
 Dhaka, Bangladesh

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 25/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Mobile communication

Description:

Mobile Bill —————→ 200₳

Approved

&

Received By

A.H.

25/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile Engineering College
 Mobile: 01717883964
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

Date: 25/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Gp internet connection

Description:

Internet Bill → 200₳

Approved
&
Received By

Anowar
25/01/16

Total → 200₳

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Mobile: 017 3248 1104
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

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 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
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 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill Date: 26/01/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post : Chairman
 Purpose : Going to Bank, Mohakhali Branch
 Description :

Lunch Bill —————> 150f

Total —> 150f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 26/01/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Mohakhali - 017 32681104
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Date : 26/01/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : Going to Bank, Mohakhali Branch

Description :

Tongi office to Mohakhali → 30f
(By Bus & Rickshaw)

Mohakhali to Tongi office → 30f

↓
Total → 60f

Approved
&
Received By

26/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Chairman
Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
Mobile: 017-22681104
Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
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 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
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 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
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Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
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Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill No: **ART LOKATION**
Shikary Art & Publicity

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain Date: 27-01-16

Address: Mobile No:

SL	Particulars	Size / Qty	Total Feet	Rate	Amount
	Stile Board 1 PCS				700
PAID					
Approved & Received By <u>[Signature]</u> 27/01/16					
Total:					700/-
Advance:					
Due:					

Taka in words:

Customer's Sign: [Signature] For Shikary Art

MohiUddin mantion, Kazi bar Road
 Gazipura, tongi, Gazipur. Mobile: 01716-946480
 01956-244586

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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KHES

কাজী হার্ডওয়্যার এড ইলেকট্রনিক্স কোর্স

শ্রোঃ কাজী রফিকুল ইসলাম

এখানে পেইন্ট, ভার্নিস, বেস্ট বেয়ারিং, তার, তারকাটা, ড্রিল মেশিন এবং যাবতীয় হার্ডওয়্যার এর মালামাল পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।

হাজী আঃ খালেদ মার্কেট, গাজীপুরা, টঙ্গী, গাজীপুর।

মোবাইল : ০১৭০৩-৯১০৪৪৮

নং	430	তারিখ :	29/02/2026
নাম :			
ঠিকানা :			
ক্রঃ নং	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	টাকা
	১. ১০০ গ্রাম	১০০ গ্রাম	২০৳
	২. ১ ডিগ্রি	১ ডিগ্রি	৬০৳
	৩. ১ ডিগ্রি	১ ডিগ্রি	২০০৳
	৪. ২ ডিগ্রি	২ ডিগ্রি	৪৳
<p>Approved & Received By</p> <p>27/02/26</p> <p>Dr. Anowar Hossain</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant</p> <p>Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc</p>			
		মোট-	২৪৪৳

টাকা (কথায়)

বিঃ দ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না।

ক্রোতার স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

27/02/26

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বিস্ময়কর বাস্তবতার স্বাক্ষর
ক্যাশ মেমো
 ফোন ০১৭২৪-৩১১২০৬
 ০১০৪৪-৩০১০০৯

এস.আলম বেডিং স্টোর
 প্লোঃ মোঃ এখলাস উদ্দিন

এখানে অটোমেটিক মেশিনে তুলা ধুলাই করে লেপ, তোষক, বালিশের কভার জাজিম, সোফা সেট, পর্দা, ইত্যাদি প্রস্তুতকারক ও সরবরাহকারী।
 কাজী মুল্লুক হোসেন রোড, গাজীপুরা, টঙ্গী, গাজীপুর।

নং: **817** তারিখ: **২২/১১/২০**

নাম: **শ্রী. শ্রী. মোঃ মাহবুব হোসেন**

ঠিকানা: **শ্রী. শ্রী. মোঃ মাহবুব হোসেন**

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
	১. ১০০০	১০		
	২০০		৪০	৮০০
	৩০০		৬০	১৮০০
	৪০০		২০০	৮০০
	৫০০			১০০
	৬০০			১০০
	৭০০			১০০
	৮০০			১০০
	৯০০			১০০
	১০০০			১০০
	১১০০			১০০
	১২০০			১০০
	১৩০০			১০০
	১৪০০			১০০
	১৫০০			১০০
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	২৯০০			১০০
	৩০০০			১০০
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	৯৮০০			১০০
	৯৯০০			১০০
	১০০০০			১০০

১৫ দিনের মধ্যে মাল জেলিভারী না নিলে কোন ক্ষতি হলে কতৃপক্ষ দায়ী নহে।

ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর: **মোঃ মাহবুব হোসেন** বিক্রিত মাল ফেরৎ লওয়া হয় না। বিক্রোক্তার স্বাক্ষর: **মোঃ মাহবুব হোসেন**

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
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 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
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 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
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 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill Date: 31/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman
 Purpose: office furniture purchasing
 Description:

Tongi office to Tongi Bazar	15₹
Tongi Bazar to Tongi office (By Bus & Rickshaw)	15₹
Total → 30₹	

Approved
 &
 Received By

31/03/16
 Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Program of Textile & Fashion
 Mobile: 01722681104
 Email: engr.anowar@rmit.edu.au

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Name : Mr. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : Office shifting by Pick-up

Description :

Tongi office to Nikunja office → 1500₹

Labour cost → 500₹

Approved & Received

By

Anowar
31/01/26

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Mobile: 01732681104
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
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ফ্যান মেমো

মোহাম্মদীয়া রেস্টুরেন্ট

এখানে উন্নতমানের খাবার যত্নসহকারে পরিবেশন করা হয়
 এবং যে কোন অনুষ্ঠানে অর্ডার সরবরাহ করা হয়।
 গাজীপুরা বাস স্ট্যান্ড, ময়মনসিংহ রোড, টঙ্গী, গাজীপুর।
 মোবাঃ ০১৭৪০-৯৫০১২৬
 ০১৯১৫-৩৮৪০৮১

তারিখ ৩১.০১.১৬

নামঃ				
ঠিকানা				
ক্রমিক নং	বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টকা
২	৩৬০ গ্রাম			২৬০/-
				২৬০/-

Approved & Received

By
31/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Institute (BTFI)
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

টিক কথায়.....

স্বাক্ষর

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01 ২০

হাওলাদার ফার্নিচার
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All Kinds of Latest T.V. Trolley, Chair, Coat Hanger And Office Furniture Retailer & Supplier
Uttara Show Room: Uttara Tower (Basement Floor), 1 Jashim Uddin Avenue, Sector # 03, Uttara, Dhaka-1230.
MOBILE: 01610-610184, 01610-610184. E-mail: & fb: hawladarfurniture@yahoo.com

সূত্র: তারিখ: ৩০-০১-১৬

১) ~~সুপার সফট~~ (H) ২২ স্ট্রুপ = ৬০০০h

২) সুপার সফট স্ট্রুপ স্ট্রুপ = ২০০h
৪০০০h

Approved By
A. Hossain
Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
International Professor & Research Consultant
Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc

৩০/০১/১৬

01683573554

স্বাক্ষর
২২/১/১৬

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
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 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

বিশ্বমিত্রাহির রাহমানির রাহমান

জম জম পেপার হাউজ এন্ড স্টেশনারী

JOM JOM PAPER HOUSE & STATIONARY

প্রোগ্রাম মোঃ গুমর ফারুক

এখানে সকল প্রকার কাগজ, খাতা, কলম, ফটোকপি পেপার, অফসেট পেপার
 ক্যালকুলেটরসহ অফিসিয়াল যাবতীয় মালামাল পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 মোবাইল : ০২-৯৮১৪৬৮৫, ০১৭৬২-৬৩১৬১৭, ০১৭৯৫-২৩৫৫২২
 সবুয়া মার্কেট, টঙ্গী বাজার, গাজীপুর মহানগর।

তারিখ: ৩০/৩/২০

নং-			
নাম	5918		
ঠিকানা			
সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	টাকা
	খোলা মালা	৫০	১০০০
	A-4 হাউজ	৫০	৭০০
	ড্রাইং হাউজ	৫০	৬০০
	A-4 ২মস্ট্যাক	৫০	২৬০
	সেভিয়ার	২৫	৭০০
	স্টেট কালি	৫০	২৬০
	কালি	৫০	২০০
	সেপারেশন	৫০	১২০
	কালি	৫০	১৫০
	গ্লাস	৫০	৪০
	কালি	৫০	৬০
	কালি	৫০	১০০
	কালি	৫০	১০০
	A-4 ২মস্ট্যাক	৫০	২৭০
কমার :			মোট: ১০০০

Approved By: ৩০/৩/২০
 ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর:
 নামাজ বেহেস্তের চাবি
 বিক্রয়ের স্বাক্ষর:
 = ১৪৭,৭৭৪#

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Date: 30/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Purchasing stationery for office

Description:

Tongi office to Tongi Bazar → 15₳
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Tongi Bazar to Tongi office → 65₳
 (By Rickshaw)

Total → 80₳

Approved
 &
 Received By

 30/01/16

Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Salary
2016- January

Date : 01/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
post : chairman

Description :

Salary of January → 50,000f

50,000f

Approved & Received By

01/02/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Department of Textile & Fashion
 School of Fashion and Textiles
 RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Office Expenditure, January, 2016

Office Salary: 50,000₹

Office Advance: 17,000₹

Furniture: 29,490₹

Conveyance: 3,650₹

Lunch: 3,134₹

Entertainment: 500₹

Office rent: 2,000₹

Office stationery: 3,604₹

Sample purchasing: 3,690₹

Purchasing poly: 100₹

Office Nameplate: 1,000₹

Mobile Bill: 2,200₹

Internet Bill: 500₹

Burner: 900₹

Hanger: 200₹

Purchasing Tray & glass for tea: 390

Trade fair Entry Ticket: 30

Bra Production: 66,360₹

Total → 1,18,388₹ + 66,360₹

= 1,84,748₹

Approved By

01.02.2016

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Bangladesh Chairman
Mobile: 017-2222-3636
E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
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Bill

Date: 01/01/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : chairman

Purpose : office Advance

Description :

Advance to House owner → 17000f
 (02 month rent)

Approved
 &
 Received By

(Signature)
 01/01/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

01

বিস্মিল্লাহির রাহমানির রাহিম

ক্যাশ মেমো

ম্যানেজারঃ ০১৭৭১-৯৩০১১৩

বিক্রমপুর ফার্নিচার Bikrampur Furniture

নং 626

এখানে সকল প্রকার ফার্নিচার সামগ্রী পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
কারখানাঃ ৫০৭/৩.৫২, ময়নারবাগ, হোসেন মার্কেট, উত্তর বাডতা, ঢাকা-১২১২
ফোন-কমঃ রোড # ১৪, গুট # ১/দি, বিল্ডিং-২, (সোটা স কাফা টাওয়ারের পাশে), ঢাকা-১২২৯।
ফোনঃ- ০১৮১৮-৪১৩১৭৪, ০১৬৭৭-১৫১৪৮৫

তারিখঃ ০২/০২/০২৬

নামঃ জিয়া মামুন হোসেন ক্রেতার মোবাঃ

ঠিকানাঃ রোড #

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
১	৫ ½ ডিগ্রি (১ টি) + ১১ ১/২ (১ টি)	১৮		
২	২০০ ডিগ্রি কাইট	১৮		
৩	১০ ডিগ্রি মামুন চেয়ার	২৮	২৪০০/	৬৭২০০
<p>৫০০০/- paid 02/02/26 Approved By 02/02/26</p>				
			মোট-	৬৭২০০
			অর্থম-	
			বাকী-	৬

টাকা কথায়ঃ

নিজে নামাজ পড়ুন, অন্যকে নামাজ পড়তে উৎসাহিত করুন।

বিঃদ্রঃ বিভিন্ন মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না

ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
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 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
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 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1

পশ্চিমবাহির রাহমানির রাহিম
 বিস্মিত্তাহির রাহমানির রাহিম
ক্যাশ মেমো মোবো : ০১৯১০-১৭২৭৭০
 : ০১৯১৯-১৭২৭৭০

মিনহাজ বেডিং স্টোর
MINHAJ BEDING STORE
প্রোগ মোঃ মিজান মিয়া

এখানে উন্নতমানের লেপ, তোষক, জাজিব, মশারী, পর্দা, বানিশের কভার, লেপের কভার
 বিছানার চাদর, ফোম কভার, ফুশন ইত্যাদি কাজ সুন্দর কারিগর দ্বারা তৈরী ও বিক্রয় করা হয়
 এবং পুরাতন কাজ রিপিংয়েরি করা হয়।

দোকান নং-২, রোড নং-১২, বিলক্ষেত টানপাড়া, নিকুঞ্জ, ঢাকা-১২২৯

নং: 74 তারিখ ২২/২/২৫

নাম ০১৭৩২৬৪১১০৮৮ ডেলিভারি তারিখ ২২/২/২৫

ঠিকানা

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
	 লাদা			২০০০
				২০০০
				৫০০
				৫০০

Approved By
 ০১৭৩২৬৪
 Md. Anwar Hossain
 Chief Scientist
 Defence & Law Research Centre
 RMIT University
 Melbourne, Australia
 Email: engr.anowar@rmit.edu.au
 Website: www.rmit.edu.au

বিঃ দ্রঃ ২১ দিনের মধ্যে মাল তেলিভারী নিতে হবে। ২১ দিন পরে মালের কোন
 ক্ষতি/নষ্ট হলে কর্তৃপক্ষ দায়ী থাকিবে না। বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না।

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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01 |

বিস্ময়কর রাহমান রাহীম

জম জম পেপার হাউজ এন্ড ষ্টেশনারী JOM JOM PAPER HOUSE & STATIONARY

ক্যাশ
মেমো

শ্রোঃ মোঃ ওমর ফারুক

এখানে সকল প্রকার কাগজ, বাতা, কলম, ফটোকপি পেপার, অফসেট পেপার
 ক্যালকুলেটরসহ অফিসিয়াল যাবতীয় মালামাল পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 মোবাইল : ০২-৯৮১৪৬৮৫, ০১৭৬২-৬৩১৬১৭, ০১৭৯৫-২৩৫৫২২
 সবুয়া মার্কেট, টঙ্গী বাজার, গাজীপুর মহানগর।

নং	5919				তারিখ	
নাম						
ঠিকানা						
সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা		
				২০৬০০		
	কিনা	২৫	৮০০	২০০০০		
	১৫৫	১৫	৮০০	১২০০০		
	<p>Approved By</p> <p>30/03/16</p>				২০৬০০	
কথায়	<p>Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain</p> <p>3820066@student.rmit.edu.au</p> <p>Mobile: 01722961194</p> <p>Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com</p>				মেটি	২০৬০০

ক্রমিক নং

নামাজ বেহেস্তের চানি

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Office Expenditure, February: 2016

- Office Salary → 50,000₹
- Office Rent → 12,000₹
- Mobile Bill → 1620₹
- Internet Bill → 1000₹
- Office Entertainment → 5790₹
- Conveyance → 2885
- Office cookery & cleaners → 2000₹
- Fan → 2650₹
- Name clearance certificate → 2000₹
- Furniture → 8000₹
- Purchasing Sample → 1220₹
- Office. Beg → 1000₹
- chemical → 9990₹
- Telephone Box → 1280₹
- Trade license → 15000₹
- Labour cost → 1620₹
- Telephone connection → 5900₹
- Miscellaneous → 53415₹
- Total → 177370₹

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Mobila Bill

Date: 01/02/15

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: office mgt.

Description:

Approved
 &
 Received By
[Signature]
 01/02/15

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
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Bill **Date: 01/02/16**

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Office Meeting

Description:

Office Entertainment → 500₳

Total → 500₳

Approved
&
Received By
Anowar
01/02/16

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Bill

Date: 02/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: office Entertainment

Description:

Coffee	→	300₳
Milk	→	200₳
Biscuit	→	100₳

|

 Total → 600₳

Approved
&
Received By

02/02/16

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 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
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 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
 Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Advance IT Technologies Limited
 1087
 Thanks with Ait. Anowar

Nikunja Office : House -1/A, Road -10, 2nd Floor, Nikunja -2,
 Dhaka-1229, Ph: 01988300970 Cell: 0190000000, 0190090000
Uttara Office : R-14/B, H-1, 3rd Floor, Uttara, Dhaka

DATE: 02 02 2016
 D D M M Y Y Y

The Sum of Taka Feb-20 TK **500 + 500**

Month of Feb-20 Installation Charge

Internet Section Software Section Domain Registration Web Hosting Training Section

Nikunja Office Uttara Office

Authorized Signature

DBBL BRAC BANK bKash

০১৭৭ ০১২৫৭৭৩১৯১

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

Date: 03/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Purchasing miscellaneous item

Description:

Tea Mog → 80₳

Sandel for washroom → 50₳

Balconi curtain → 300₳

Total → 430₳

Approved

&

Received By

A.H.

03/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

7/18

Conveyance Bill

Date: 05/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Natayangong for order placement.

Description:

Nikunja office to Noyamati → 70₳
 Noyamati to Nikunja office → 70₳
 (By Bus & Kickstaco)

Total → 140₳

Approved
 &
 Received By
 Af
 05/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Tea Bill

Date: 05/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : Going to Natrayangong for order placement.

Description :

Tea Bill → 20₳

Total → 20₳

Approved

&

Received By

[Signature]

05/02/16

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 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 05/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : chairman

Purpose : office cooking

Description :

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 05/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Lunch Bill

Date: 05/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to Natogyangong

Description:

Lunch Bill → 150₳

Approved

&

Received By

A. Hossain

05/02/16

Total → 150₳

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
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"স্বিস্টাফিকি বাস্তবায়িত্বি বাস্তবায়িত্বি"
পাওয়ার হাউজ
POWER HOUSE
 for electric & kitchen needs
 গণমানে সকল ধরনের ম্যান, হার্ডওয়্যার লাইট, গ্যাসের লুপসং যন্ত্রপাতি।
 ইলেকট্রিক মালামাল ও প্রাদিক সামগ্রী বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 বাড়ী # ৫০, রোড # ১২, নিকুন্-২, ঢাকা-১২২০।
ভাউচার

ফোন: ৫০২-২০০৬৬৬
 মোবাইল: ৫০১১২৬০৬৬৬৬

নাম: _____ তারিখ: ০৫/০২/১৬

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	টাকা
ক)	কম্পাউন্ড — ০১	২৭৫/-
খ)	লুপসং যন্ত্র — ০১	২০০/-
		মোট: ৪৭৫/-

ধন্যবাদ আশীর্বাদসহ।
 কোম্পানির স্বাক্ষর

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Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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01 25

Bill

Date: 06/02/15

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Purchasing Towel

Description:

Office Towel (02 pcs) → 450F

Total → 450F

Approved
&
Received By

06/02/15

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 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 06/02/15

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post : chairman
 Purpose : Electrical maintenance
 Description :

Approved
 &
 Received By
 A.H.
 06/02/15

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Conveyance Bill

Date: 07/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Banarasi for market survey

Description:

Nikunja office to Banarasi, Binadini → 40₹
shopping complex

Banarasi to Nikunja office → 40₹
(By Bus & Rickshaw)

Approved
&

Received By

Anowar
07/02/16

Total → 80₹

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
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 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill Date: 07/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Market Survey

Description:

Lunch Bill (02 Person)	300f
Total → 300f	

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 07/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Date: 08/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : Going to Registrar office of joint stock company .

Description :

Nikunja office to Kawranbazar → 80f

Kawranbazar to Nikunja office → 80f

(By Bus & Rickshaw)
02 person

Approved
&
Received By
[Signature]
08/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
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 Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing &
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 Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Date: 09/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : chairman

Purpose : Going to Telephone office

Description :

Nikunja office to Azampur, Ullaha → 30₳
 (By Bus & Rickshaw - 02 person)

Azampur, Ullaha to Nikunja office → 30₳

↑
 Total → 60₳

Approved
 &
 Received By

Anowar
 09/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

01 | ✉

Lunch Bill

Date: 09/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : chairman

Purpose : Going to Telephone office

Description :

Lunch Bill → 300f
 (02 person)

Total → 300f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 09/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill Date: 09/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to registration office of joint stock company.

Description:

Lunch Bill (02 person) → 300₳

Total → 300₳

Approved & Received By

[Signature]
09/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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01/25

নিম্নলিখাতিব কাছমানির বারিসিহা

Bill

Date : 09/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : chairman

Purpose : Purchasing Sample

Description :

Approved
&
Received By
A
09/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
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 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission);
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur,
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
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Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

বিক্রমপুর ফার্নিচার

Bikrampur Furniture

এখানে সকল প্রকার ফার্নিচার সামগ্রী পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 কারখানা : ৫০৭/৩.৫২, ময়নাববাগ, হোসেন মার্কেট, উত্তর বাজড়া, ঢাকা-১২১২
 শো-রুম : রোড # ১৪, গুট # ১/সি, বিল্ডিং-২, (লোটাস কমাল টাওয়ারের পাশে), ঢাকা-১২২৯।

671 ফোনঃ- ০১৮১৮-৪১৩১৭৪, ০১৬৭৭-১৫১৪৮৫

তারিখ ৩/০২/২০২০

নং	নাম	ফ্রেমের মোতা			
	জোয়াবন্দার	৩২			
	ঠিকানা	হোসেন মার্কেট	বাড়ি	৩২	

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
১	জোয়াবন্দার চেয়ার	৩২	২০০/-	৬৬০০/-
				মোট- ৬৬০০/-
				অগ্রিম-
				বাকী- ৬৬০০/-

টাকা কথায়ঃ.....

নিজে নামাজ পড়ুন, অন্যকে নামাজ পড়তে উৎসাহিত করুন।

বিঃদ্রঃ বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না

ফ্রেমের স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

Cite: N

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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বিস্মিত্তাহির রাহমানির রাহিম

ক্যাশ মেমো

ম্যানেজারঃ ০১৭৭১-৯৩০১১৩

বিক্রমপুর ফার্নিচার Bikrampur Furniture

এখানে সকল প্রকার ফার্নিচার সামগ্রী পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
কারখানা : ৫০৭/৩.৫২, ময়নারবাগ, হোসেন মার্কেট, উত্তর বাডজা, ঢাকা-১২১২
ফোন-রুমঃ রোড # ১৪, গুট # ১/সি, খিলক্ষেত, বিকল্প-২, (লোটার্স কামাল টাওয়ারের পার্শ্ব), ঢাকা-১২১৯।

৬৭৩ মোঃ- ০১৮১৮-৪১৩১৭৪, ০১৬৭৭-১৫১৪৮৫

নং

তারিখ ১১/০২/২০১৬

নাম মোঃ জিয়াবুল হক ক্রেতার মোবা .

ঠিকানা রোড # ১০ বাস # ২২

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
২/	৩৬x৩৮ ডায়নিম টেবিল	২৫	২৭০০/-	২৭০০/-
				মোট- ২৭০০/-
				অগ্রিম- 11
				বাকী-

বাকী = ২৭০০/-

টাকা কথায় ৪.....

নিজে নামাজ পড়ুন, অন্যকে নামাজ পড়তে উৎসাহিত করুন।

নিঃসৃত বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না

ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
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 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur,
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

ক্যাশ মেমো

চন্দন টেক্সটাইল CHANDAN TEXTILE

উন্নতমানের টিম্পার্ট পাইকারী বিক্রেতা।
২নং নয়ামাটি, গিরীধারী মার্কেট, নারায়ণগঞ্জ।

ফোন : ০২-৭৬৪৪৭৯১, মোবা : ০১৮১৯-১২৯৬৪৫, ০১৭১২-৮১৩৯৭৪, ০১৮১৪-০৯৫৮৯১

নং	03	তারিখ	২০/০২/২০২৩		
নাম	শ্রী: জাহাঙ্গীর হোসেন				
ঠিকানা					
নং	মালের বিবরণ	ডজন	পিছ	দর	টাকা
০১	০২/০৪ সামান্য জোড়		৬৮	৩৭০	২০২৫
টাকা কথায় :				মোট-	২০২৫
ক্রয়ের স্বাক্ষর					বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
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০১

বিল অফিস - ৭৬৩৩৫৩৭

আনন্দ রেস্টোরাঁ

৪ শহীদ সোহরাওয়ার্দী রোড, নারায়ণগঞ্জ।

নং 454 তারিখ ২০/২/২০২৪

নামঃ

ক্রমিক	বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
	কিচেন	২২০ম	২২০	২৪০৮
			মোট	২৪০৮

স্বাক্ষর: *[Signature]*
 পক্ষে - আনন্দ রেস্টোরাঁ

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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill Date: 10/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to factory, Narayanganj.

Description:

Nikunja office to factory —————→ 260f
 (02 person)

Factory to Nikunja office —————→ 260f
 (By Bus & Rickshaw & Leguna)

Total → 520f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 10/02/16

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Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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*Relation for Some times but friend ship for long time
"we believe in friend ship"*

Shop No-27, London Plaza, Uttara Model Town, Dhaka-1230

No.- **4142** Cell : **01720-883143** Date : *22/2/20*

Name :

Address :

Sl. No.	Description	Qty.	Rate	Taka
	<i>গরুর চামড়া</i>	<i>2</i>		<i>2000/-</i>
Taka in Word			Total Tk: <i>2000/-</i>	

Customer's Signature _____ *শহিদুল হোসেন*
 Authorised Signature _____

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 11/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Ulhazra buying office

Description:

Lunch Bill (02 person) → 350₳

350₳
Total → 350₳

Approved
&
Received By
A. Anowar
11/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Conveyance Bill

Date : 11/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post : chairman
 Purpose : Purchasing office Bag

Description :

Nikunja office to Tongi Bazar → 25f
 Tongi Bazar to office → 25f

|
 Total → 50f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 11/02/16

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 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 12/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : Purchasing miscellaneous item

Description :

Paposh (02 pcs)	→	600₹
RFL knife	→	200₹
Biscuit	→	150₹
TEA	→	120₹
Milk	→	150₹
Sugar	→	20₹
Electric Balb	→	50₹
Electric Mixer	→	2700₹
Hanger - 06 pcs	→	84₹
<hr/>		
Total →		4174₹

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 12/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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01 | 20

Lunch Bill

Date: 13/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Binadini shopping complex

Description:

Approved
&
Received By
A. Hossain
13/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill Date: 13/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Going to Binadini market.

Description:

Nikunja office to BANARSI → 60₹
 BANARSI to Nikunja office → 60₹
 (By Bus & Rickshaw - 02 person)

Total → 120₹

Approved
 &
 Received By

 13/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Lunch Bill

Date: 14/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairmen

Purpose: Going to Bank, Mohakhali

Description:

Approved
 &
 Received By

 14/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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3/3

Conveyance Bill

Date: 14/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to Bank, Mohakhali & Post office, Banani

Description:

Nikunja office to Bank, Mohakhali → 50₹
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Bank, Mohakhali to Nikunja office → 20₹
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

↑
 Total → 70₹

Approved
 &
 Received By

 14/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date : 15/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Office Guest Entertainment

Description:

Entertainment → 500₳
(03 person)

Approved
&
Received By

15/02/16

Total → 500₳

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
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 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
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 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
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 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
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Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

01

Bill

Date : 15/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Purchasing office Miscellaneous Item

Description:

Correction pen	—————→	40₳
Thread	—————→	30₳
Electrical switch	—————→	120₳
Small scissor (02 pcs)	—————→	60₳
Small scale	—————→	20₳
	—————	
	Total →	270₳

Approved
 &
 Received By

 15/02/16

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Bill

Date: 15/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Purchasing office miscellaneous item

Description:

Laptop	→	35,000₹
Mobile	→	8,000₹
Small Fan	→	800₹
Cooking instrument	→	500₹
Toilet Brush & Bucket	→	350₹
Office File	→	300₹
Napkin	→	50₹
Sandel	→	60₹
Floor cleaner	→	400₹
Iron	→	600₹
Diatry	→	150₹
Multipluck (02 pcs)	→	450₹
Basket	→	60₹
Staplers	→	120₹
Punching m/c	→	100₹
		Total → 46,940₹

15/02/16

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আনোয়ার হোসেন ডিফেন্স গ্যারামেন্ট প্রাইভেট লিমিটেড

কম্পিউটার সাইন্সিং, কম্পিউটার কন্ট্রোল, ইন্টারনেট, ফ্রান্ডিস, ট্রেন্ডিং, ডিজিট, সেমিওটিক, ফটোগ্রাফি,
 স্টেশনারী, বেলনা সাফটী। মোত নং-১০, কার্জি নং-২৩, বিল্ডিং-২, মিনুস্কট, ঢাকা-১২২৯।

নামঃ **ANOWER HOSSAIN** তারিখ - **15/02/16**

ঠিকানাঃ

ক্রমিক নং	মানের বিবরণ	দর	পরিমাণ	টাকা
	Print +	20	20	20
	Seam			
মোট টাকা =				20

টাকা (কথায়) 5000
 প্রকৃত সাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার সাক্ষর

15/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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CHALLAN & MONEY RECEIPT

(SRO No. 17-A/N/2004/423-MUSA/ Dated-10/06/2004)

Musak-11

B. No. 18897 **Sl. No. 984833**

Name of Firm : DHL Worldwide Express (Bangladesh) Private Ltd.
 Address : Moly Capita Centre (Level 4 & 5), 78, Bir Uttam Mir Showket Road, Gulshan-1, Dhaka-1212, Ph. 9895810, Fax : 8823248, 8817406
 VAT Reg. No. : 18141005168

Date: 15-02-16

Customer Name : Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Address : _____
 Customer's VAT Identification No. : _____

Cash / Cheque No. : _____ Cheque Date : _____ Bank : _____

ACCOUNT NO.	INVOICE / HAWB NO.	INV/HAWB DT.	VALUE OF SERVICES	NET AMOUNT (TK.)	TOTAL AMOUNT (TK.)
Dhaka	D 01022579				1990/-
CUSTOMER COPY					
Amounts in word : <u>one thousand nine hundred and ninety taka</u>					TOTAL 1990/-
Other Deductions : _____					Net Receipt : <u>only</u>
Customer's Signature : <u>[Signature]</u>					Seller's Signature & Date : <u>[Signature]</u>

Hot Lines: +88 0192 111 2222, +88 02 9881700, 9886305, 8835804, 1635916161
 Banani: 02-9822276 Uttara: 02-892329 K.Bazar: 02-9153930 DOHS: 02-58813129 Agrabad: 001-2522271-4 Narayanganj: 021-8954514 Gulshan-2: 02-9825555 Kuril: 02-241818 Mirzapur: 02-9754511 Gajipur: 02-9264240
 Moulvibazar: 02-9533511 Dhanmondi: 02-55610895 Mirpur: 02-9022411 Rajshahi: 02-8817846 Narayanganj: 02-7450384 Sylhet: 021-711618 R.K. Mission Road: 02-9511256 Shamoli: 02-9124242
 Bogura: 8805157159 Kaulibazar: 88086164083 Tejgaon Aangri: 01929997026 Umra Aangri: 01929997022 Comilla: 01711-431024 Khulna: 041-724711 Country Office: 02-9698181 Tejgaon: 02-9698181

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill Date: 15/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Purchasing chemical

Description:

Fragrance finished chemical → 8000f

Approved
&
Received By

15/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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১১ম

আব্রাহাম কম্পিউটার গ্যাভ স্টুডিও

কম্পিউটার হার্ডওয়্যার, সফটওয়্যার কনসাল্টিং, ইন্সটলমেন্ট, স্ক্যানিং, প্রিন্টিং, ডিজিটাল, লেআউট, মাল্টিমিডিয়া, সফটওয়্যার, স্টেশনারি, বেনার, প্যামফ্লিট। রোড নং- ১০, কাজী নূর-এ-হক, পিক-২, মিলফোর্ড, ঢাকা-১২১১।

নামঃ anowar তারিখ - 15/02/16

ঠিকানাঃ

ক্রমিক নং	স্বালের বিবরণ	দর	পরিমাণ	টাকা	
	print out	10		10	১০৳
					২০৳
					৩০৳
					১৫৳
					৩০৳
					১০৳
					০০৳
					০০৳
মোট টাকা =				10+10	

টাকা (কথায়) Sagor Army

স্বাক্ষরিত কর্তৃক বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

Approved
&
Received By
Arnob
16/02/16

Total → 415৳

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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আনোয়ার কম্পিউটার প্রাইন্ট স্টুডিও

কম্পিউটার সফটওয়্যার, হার্ডওয়্যার, স্ক্যানিং, প্রিন্টিং, ডিজিটাল, লেআউট, ফটোসেপ,
 কপিমাশিনী, বেসলা স্ক্যানার। মোব নং-১০, কার্য নং-২৩, লিফট-২, মিনসেফ, হাটা-১২১৯।

নামঃ Anowar তারিখঃ 15/02/16

ঠিকানাঃ

ক্রমিক নং	মালিকের বিবরণ	নং	পরিমাণ	টাকা
	print	10		10
	out			10
				20
				30
				15
				30
				10
				20
				20
মোট টাকা =				10+10

টাকা (কথায়) Sagor Amr

Approved
 &
 Received By
 16/02/16

Total → 415

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Date: _____

আবু সাহাব হুসাইন গ্যারান্টিড ফুন্ডিং

ফাংশনাল সার্ভিস, কম্পিউটার কন্সল্ট, ইন্টারনেট, ফ্যানিং, ইন্ডিং, ডিজিট, সোল্ডারিং, স্ট্রিকিং, স্টেমিং, সোল্ডারিং, সোল্ডারিং। মোবাইল: ১৬০২-১০, ফোন নং-২৩, বিল্ডিং-২, বিল্ডিং, ৬৬৬-১২২৬।

নাম: **SAGOR** তারিখ: **16/02/16**

ঠিকানা: _____

ক্রমিক নং	মালের বিবরণ	দর	পরিমাণ	টাকা
	Photo Copy			→ 120f → 30f → 15f → 30f → 20f → 100f → 100f
মোট টাকা =				15
টাকা (কথায়) _____				
ক্রয়ের স্বাক্ষর				 বিক্রয়ের স্বাক্ষর

Total → 415

Approved
&
Received By

16/02/16

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, product analysis and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com, s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 5 March 2026.

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 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
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 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
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Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25: School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 16/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post : Chairman

Purpose: Purchasing Trade License form & others

Description :

Form price	—————→	120f
Tiffin	—————→	30f
Print	—————→	15f
Photocopy	—————→	30f
Mobile	—————→	20f
Office Entertainment	—————→	100f
Carrying chair	—————→	100f

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Lunch Bill

Date: 16/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : chairman

Purpose : Going to Telephone office

Description :

Lunch Bill → 150f

Approved
&
Received By
A. Hossain
16/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill **Date: 16/02/16**

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to Telephone office

Description:

Nikunja office to Telephone office	→ 30f
Telephone office to Nikunja office	→ 30f
Total → 60f	

Approved
&
Received By
[Signature]
16/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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01

বিস্মিত্রাহির রাহমানির রাহিম

ক্যাশ মেমো

ম্যানেজারঃ ০১৭৭১-৯৩০১১৩

বিক্রমপুর ফার্নিচার Bikrampur Furniture

এখানে সকল প্রকার ফার্নিচার সামগ্রী পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
কারখানাঃ ৫০৭/৩.৫২, মরনারবাগ, হোসেন মার্কেট, উত্তর বাডডা, ঢাকা-১২১২
ফো-কমঃ বোড # ১৪, রুট # ১/সি, বিনহেড, নিকুম-২, (নোটিস কামাল টাওয়ার পার্শে), ঢাকা-১২২৪।
ফোঃ- ০১৮১৮-৪১৩১৭৪, ০১৬৭৭-১৫১৪৮৫

নং 697

তারিখ ১৬/০২/২০১৬

নাম	শে. সাদেকার	ফোনের নং
ঠিকানা	বোড # ১৫	বস # = ১২

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
১/	জর্জিয়ান স্টোল চেয়ার	৪৮	৩০০০/	৩০০০/-
	মোট- ৩০০০/-			
	অগ্রিম-			
	বাকী-			৩০০০/-

টাকা কথায়ঃ

নিজে নামাজ পড়ুন, অন্যকে নামাজ পড়তে উৎসাহিত করুন।

বিঃ দ্রঃ বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না

ফোনের স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anwar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

"স্বিস্তিকারিত বাংলাদেশি চাকরি"

পাওয়ার হাউজ

POWER HOUSE

for electric & kitchen needs

এখানে সকল প্রকার ফ্যান, চাকুরি লাইট, ৭৫ সেরা ঘুসাসহ যাবতীয়
ইলেকট্রিক মালামাল ও পারিষ্কার সামগ্রী বিক্রয় করা হয়।
বাড়ী # ৬০, রোড # ১২, বিহুল-২, ঢাকা-১২২৯।

ভাউচার

নাম: _____ তারিখ: ৩৬/১২/১৬

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	টাকা
৬৬	ইলেকট্রিক সামগ্রী স্বতন্ত্র-৩০	৬৬০
মোট		৬৬০

স্বাক্ষরিত/স্বাক্ষরিত

Alomara

স্বাক্ষরিত/স্বাক্ষরিত

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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KHAN WATCH & GIFT GALLERY Cash Memo

Shop No. 31 (Ground Floor)
 Rajuk Commercial Complex, Uttara, Dhaka.

KHAN ELECTRONICS
 All Kinds of Electronics TV, DVD & Speaker
 Shop No. 19, 20, 31, 32 (2nd Floor)
 Rajuk Commercial Complex, Uttara, Dhaka.
 Cell : 01758944488, 01819462909

KHAN GIFT CORNER-1
 All Kinds of Cosmetics & Emulation Jewellery
 Shop # 20, 21, Rajuk Commercial Complex
 (G.F.), Uttara, Dhaka-1230.
 ☎ 02-8962346, 01819462909

Memo No. 2387

Date: 18 / 02 / 2016

Name: _____
 Address: _____

Qty.	Description	Model No.	Rate	Amount
①	Parra servie, Battapay. 3.1.13.	T8880 8880 AA	1250₳ / 30₳	1250₳ 30₳
Total Tk.				1280₳

● NO RETURN ● NO EXCHANGE ● NO GUARANTEE

Customer's Signature

For: KHAN WATCH/KHAN GIFT CORNER/KHAN ELECTRONICS

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

01/23

Bill

Date: 18/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Trade License

Description:

Trade license fees → 9000₳

Filling cost → 6000₳

Total → 15000₳

Approved
 &
 Received By
 Anowar
 18/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill & Tiffin

Date: 18/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Trade License

Description:

Lunch Bill —————→ 300₹
(02 person)

Tiffin —————→ 60₹
(02 person)

Approved
&
Received By
[Signature]
18/02/16

Total → 360₹

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing &
 process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴
 Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
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 Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
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Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Date: 18/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Trade License

Description:

Nikunja office to Ulbatta → 30f
 (By Bus & Rickshaw
 02 person)

Ulbatta to Nikunja office → 30f

Approved
 &
 Received By
(Signature)
 18/02/16

Total → 60f

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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০১

বিল অফিস - ৭৬৩৩৫৩৭

আনন্দ রেস্তোরাঁ

৪ শহীদ সোহরাওয়ার্দী রোড, নারায়নগঞ্জ।

নং 493 তারিখ ০৭.০২.২৬

নাম :

ক্রমিক নং	বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
	মিষ্ণু -	২	২২০	২৪০
	ফোর এসসী	৭	৬০	৬০
Paid				
			মোট	২৭০

পক্ষে - আনন্দ রেস্তোরাঁ

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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill Date: 19/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Gotoing to Natragyongong

Description:

Nikunja office to Natragyongong (By Bus & Rickshaw - 02 person)	165/-
Natragyongong to Nikunja office (02-person & goods cartaying cost)	310/-
Road Tax	20/-
Total	495/-

Approved
&
Received By
[Signature]
19/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

Date: 19/02/16

Name: M^r. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Catering Goods

Description:

LABOUR COST → 320/-

Approved

Received By

TII - I

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

01/26

Bill

Date: 19/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: office entertainment

Description:

office guest entertainment → 140/-

Approved
 &
 Received By

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 19/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Font: chaitman

Purpose: Mobile Bill

Description:

Mobile - Gsp → 320₳

Approved
&
Received By
Asif
19/02/16

Total → 320₳

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

01 23

Lunch Bill

Date: 22-02-16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to Narayanganj

Description:

Lunch Bill - 02 person → 300f

Approved
 &
 Received By
 Anowar
 22/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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01

Conveyance Bill

Date: 22-02-16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose : Going to Natayangong

Description :

Nikunja office to Noyamati → 160₹
(By Bus & Rickshaw)
02 person

Noyamati to Nikunja office → 510₹
(Goods carting)

22/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

01

Bill

Date : 22/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post : chairman
 Purpose : Telephone connection
 Description :

Telephone connection → 5900f
 &
 Filling cost for officers

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 22/02/16

Total → 5900f

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

Date: 23/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: office miscellaneous

Description:

Soap → 30f

Fitzbox → 20f

Lock & Lock ring → 96f

Locker pin → 5f

Water Bottle → 30f
(02 pcs)

Total → 181f

Approved

&

Received By

A. I.

23/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
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 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
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 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 29/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Going to BTCL office
 Description:

Lunch Bill → 150₹

Approved
 &
 RECEIVED BY
 Aash

Total → 150₹

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

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Conveyance Bill

Date : 23/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to City corporation

Description:

Nikunja office to Uttara → 25₹
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Uttara to Nikunja office → 25₹

Approved
 &
 Received By
Anowar
 23/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

Date: 23/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Office Guest Entertainment.

Description:

Office Guest (02 person)

Entertainment cost → 300₳

Approved

&

Received By

23/02/16

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 23/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman
 Purpose: office Labour cost
 Description:

Approved &
 Received By
 Anowar
 23/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Mobile Bill

Date: 26/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Mobile Bill

Description:

Office communication → 1000f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 26/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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Research address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25: School of Fashion
and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1

ZAFRAN Restaurant
 House # 04, Road # 01, Nikunja-2, Dhaka-1228
 Mobile: 01683 191819

T No.- **2640** Date: **27/02/16**

No	Item Name	Quantity	Price
১	কুটি / পুরটা		
২	সিলপনা / সমুদ্র / কাটকোট		
৩	জাজি / ডাল / ডাল-জাজি		
৪	চিকেন সুপ / সিল কলিঙ্গা		
৫	চিকেন মানসান / আল ফ্রাই / সোপেয়াজে / ভুনা / রোস্ট / আল মুব্বী		
৬	গরু- নেহরী / কালা ভুনা / ভুনা / ছাপ		60
৭	খামি- কলিঙ্গা / পায় / ভুনা / খামির ডাল / গামি		
৮	ভর্তা / ভাজি / ফটকি ভর্তা / ওটকি ভুনা / মাউ সিংডি / কাফুরী		
৯	বিচড়ী চিকেন / বিফ / মাটন/ হালিস		
১০	চিকেন বিরিয়ানী / কাফি বিরিয়ানী / খাদা ভাত (কাটাই)		
১১	নই / ইলিশ / কে / বাহিলা / শৈল / মেংড়া মাছ		
১২	বোয়াল / পাবনা / চিংড়ি / বাইস / রুপচানা মাছ		
১৩	নান / পরোসি (প্রেইন / বাটার) / গরলিক নান		
১৪	মোপনাই / স্পেশাল মোপনাই / কিয়া মোপনাই		
১৫	চিকেন ভন্দুরী / চিকেন টিরা (দেশী/ব্রয়লার) / চিকেন বটি		
১৬	বিফ শিক কাবার / মাটন বটি কাবার		
১৭	গ্রীল চিকেন- ফুল / হাফ / কোমটার / চিকেন শর্মা		
১৮	লাজি / ফালুদা / বোপহাশী / পুডিং / নই / কিম্বি		
১৯	চা / কফি / সফট ড্রিঙ্কস / মিনারেল ওয়াটার / ফিস্টার ওয়াটার		
২০	অন্যান্য		
২১			
		মোট	

২৭/০২/১৬

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Office Salary

Date: 27/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Monthly Salary

Description:

Salary of February: 16 → 50,000₹

Total → 50,000₹

Approved

&

Received By

[Signature]

27/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
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Bill

Date : 28/02/16

Name ; Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Labour cost

Description :

Label joining & Box entry of product → 1000f

Total → 1000f

Approved
&
Received By

A
28/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

Date: 28/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: company registration

Description:

Name clearance certificate → 1500₳

legal consultant → 500₳

Approved
&

Received By

A. Hossain

28/02/16

Total → 2000₳

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 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

01 23 **Bill** **Date: 29/02/16**

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
Post: chairman

Purpose: Office Entertainment

Description:

Lunch Bill → 490f
(03 person)

Tiffin → 60f

Total → 550f

Approved & Received By
Aaab
29/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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House rent

Date: 29/02/2016

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: House rent & related others

Description:

House rent (including all Bills) → 12,000f

Approved

&

Received By

Abub

29/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Date: 03/03/26

Bill

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Expenditure of March

Description:

Office Salary	→	56452₹
Conveyance	→	1158₹
Office Entertainment	→	9525₹
Newspaper	→	300₹
Internet Bill	→	500₹
Mobilia Bill	→	500₹
Brca & Panty Set	→	840₹
House rent	→	12000₹
Bag	→	4200₹
Fragrance chemical	→	8500₹
Postal Sending	→	2640₹
TIN ID	→	1500₹
PT/Insurance	→	22920₹
		Total → 111845₹

Approved by
 [Signature]
 03/03/26

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Bill

০৫/০৪/১৬

Md. Jahid Hossain

past Assistant merchandiser

Description

মঞ্জিল মার্চেন্ট হাউস
 মার্চেন্ট হাউস ডেলারী
 ৬৪৬২ ঢাকা

Approved by

 ০৫/০৪/১৬

Recd by

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Bill

1/03/16

লাঞ্চ লাভ বিল -
 Lunch ————— 30 F
 ২-ভাত ————— 40 F
 ২-কব্বা বাজী ————— 10 F
 ৩-ডাল ————— 80 F

Approved by

[Signature]
 1/03/16

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স্বাক্ষরিত

তারিখ

02-03-16

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৩১০৫ ১০ -	10
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	300

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মা হার্ডওয়ার ইলেকট্রিক এ্যান্ড স্যানিটারি

কাশ বেমো

এখানে হার্ডওয়ার, ইলেকট্রিক এবং স্যানিটারি মলামাল, জি. আই. পাইপ, পি.ভি. সি পাইপ, কিচিংস, কমেড, বেসিং সুলভ মূল্যে নিজেরা করা হয়।
 বাড়ি নং-৩৪, রোড নং-২, নিকুল-২, ঢাকা-১২২৯

মোবাইল :
 ০১৭১৪-৩৭১৯২২
 ০১৭৩৬-৭৬৯৩৮৪
 ০১৭৩০-৫২২৩২৪

নং:	8212				তারিখ:	02/06/23
নাম:						
ঠিকানা:						
ক্রঃ নং	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	মোট		
১	TNT বক্স -	৪০	৪০	৪০		
২	TNT বক্স -	৩০	৩০	৩০		
৩				৭০		
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১৭	ধন্যবাদ আবার আসবেন।				৭০	

বিঃ দ্রঃ বিক্রিত মাল ফেরৎ সংগ্রহা হয়ে না।
 নিজের নামাঙ্ক পড়ুন, অন্যরকম নামাঙ্ক পড়তে উৎসাহিত নয়।

ফোনের স্মারক-

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ঢাকা স্পাইস হোটেল এন্ড রেস্টুরেন্ট Dhaka Spice Hotel And Restaurant

কবি ফারুক স্মরণী, নিকুল-০২, খিলক্ষেত (রাজউক মার্কেট সংলগ্ন), ঢাকা-১২২৯
মোবাইল : ০১৬৮২ ৩০৫৩৮৮, ০১৮২২-৮০৭৬৩৩

নং- 2957 টেবিল নং..... তারিখ : ৪/৩/১৬

নাম :

বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
G. Chicken	2	80	160
P. nam	2	20	40
water	1	-	15
			205
		মোট	
		অস্বীকৃত	
		বাকী	

টাকা (কথায়) :

স্বাক্ষর-

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Bill

Date: 05/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: mobile recharge

Description:

Flexi load → 500f

Approved
 &
 Received By
 AS
 05/03/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

Date: 05/03/26

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Miscellaneous

Description:

Rubbers	—————→	20₳
Label printing	—————→	30₳
Pen - 03 pens	—————→	30₳
Pen (signature - 06 pens)	—————→	30₳
	Total →	110₳

Approved
 &
 Received By

 05/03/26

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date : 06/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post : chairman
 Purpose : Lunch Bill for marketing
 Description :

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 06/03/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date : 06/03/26

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : chairman

Purpose : office cleaning & cooking

Description :

Office cleaner → 2000f

Total → 2000f

Approved
&
Received By

06/03/26

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Bill

Date : 06/03/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : chairman

Purpose : Office Entertainment

Description :

Coffee	_____	300f
Milk	_____	220f
Biscuit	_____	200f
Fruit	_____	450f
Water Bottle	_____ →	30f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 06/03/16

↓

 Total → 1200f

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Bill

Date: 06/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: office Entertainment

Description:

office Guest fooding → 300f

Approved
 &
 Received By
Ans
 06/03/16

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পাওয়ার হাউজ
POWER HOUSE
 for electronic & kitchen needs
 এখানে সকল ধরনের ফ্যান, চার্জার লাইট, পায়ের জুতাশব্দ যাবতীয়
 ইলেকট্রিক মালামাল ও প্রাচীর সামগ্রী বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 বাড়ী # ৫৩, রোড # ১২, বিল্ডিং-২, ফলা-১২২৯।

ডাউটার
 তারিখ: ০৭/০৩/২৬
 নাম: _____

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	টাকা
#	লাসিবি চ্যামের কাপ ৬ পিসি	২৫০/-
	<i>Signature</i>	

মোট = ২৫০/-
 প্রদান
 প্রস্তুতকারকের স্বাক্ষর
 বিক্রয়কারকের স্বাক্ষর

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বিস্মিত্যাহির স্বাক্ষরিত রসিদ

মায়ের দোয়া ভ্যারাইটিস স্টোর

এখানে চাউল, মুদি, ষ্টেশনারী প্রভৃতি যে কোন অনুষ্ঠানের মাধ্যমে
 অর্ডার নেওয়া হয় এবং পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়

(মোঃ মোঃ মনোয়ার খান (মালিক))

১২নং রাস্তার মাথায়, মাতাঝর মার্কেট, নিকুল-২, বিলক্ষেত্র, ঢাকা।
 মোবাইল: ০১৭১২-০৭১৩০১, ০১৯২৯-৬০৯০৪৮

সূত্রঃ _____ তারিখঃ ১/৬/২৬

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	টাকা
	৬১ ২৮	৭০
		৭০
	মোট	
	অগ্রীম	
	বাকী	

স্বাক্ষর

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AIT
Advance IT Technologies Limited

1389

Nikunja Office: House -1/A, Road -12, 2nd Floor, Nikunja -2,
 Dhaka-1229, Ph: 01983300970 Cell: 01619090000, 01190090000
Uttara Office: R-14/B, H-1, 3rd Floor, Sector-4, Uttara, Dhaka

DATE: 09 03 2016
 D D M M Y Y Y Y

Thanks with: ait: Anwar

The Sum of Taka _____ TK 500/-

Month of Mar-16 Installation Charge _____

- Internet Section Software Section Domain Registration Web Hosting Training Section
 Nikunja Office Uttara Office

Monir
 Authorized Signature

* প্রতিস্থাপন ব্যয় অপেক্ষম যোগ্য;
 * প্রতি মাসে ১ তারিখের মধ্যে এই মাসের বিদ্য পেমেন্ট করতে হবে।
 * সেবা টি বন্ধ করতে হলে অবশ্যই ১ (এক) মাস পূর্বে জানাতে হবে

bKash : 01925773191

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Bill

Date: 09/03/16

Md: Jahid Hossain

post: Assistant-Merchandiser

Purpose: marketing conveyance

Description:

Nikunja office to Chok Bazar → 30F

New marketing Nikunja office → 30F

|
 Total → 60F

Approved By
 [Signature]
 10/03/16

Received By

[Signature]
 10-03-16

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Bill

Date: 13/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to Singura, Keraniganj

Description:

Nikunja office to Keraniganj → 140f
 (02 person)
 Keraniganj to Nikunja office → 150f

Total → 290f

Approved
 &
 Received By
 Aab
 13/03/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

01

বিল

ad put
13-03-16

Md: জাহিদ হাভান

পোস্ট: এডমিন সারজুন জাহিদ

প্রাপ্ত : খিলখেল থেকে আনুলী → ২০৮

বাস্তা থেকে মৌচাক → ০৬

মৌচাক থেকে খিলখেল → ২০
 মোটাল ৩২৮

→ প্রাপ্তি করে

Approved By

K-03-16

Received By

14-03-16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
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 Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

বিল

তারিখ-14-08-16

মো: জাহিদ হাজার

প্রোফে এচিভমেন্ট স্মারটের জাহিদ হাজার

অপেক্ষ: স্মিল ডেস্ক থেকে মনুনা পার্ক → ১০F

ভুলকান থেকে বাজা বিবিজ → ১০F

বাজা থেকে বনশ্রী → ১০F

বনশ্রী থেকে স্মিল ডেস্ক → ১০F
 স্টাফ রুম ১০

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Bill

Date: 15/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman

Purpose: Office Entertainment

Description:

Coffee	_____	300₳
Milk	_____	220₳
Fruit	_____	100₳
Biscuit	_____	100₳
		Total → 720₳

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 &
 Received By

 15/03/16

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 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 15/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Parcel Sending

Description:

Parcel to Andia —————> 2000₳
 Parcel to Natayangong —————> 80₳
 Parcel to Sadarqhat —————> 80₳

2160₳

Approved
 &
 Received By
 Anowar
 15/03/16

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SUNDARBAN COURIER SERVICE (PVT.) LTD সুন্দরবন কুরিয়ার সার্ভিস (প্রাঃ) লি: HEAD OFFICE : 24-25, DILKUSHA C/A, DHAKA TEL : 9551696, 9559935, 9559952 FAX : 88-02-9553995, E-mail : scs@citetechno.net				NON-NEGOTIABLE কনসাইনমেন্ট CONSIGNMENT NOTE কনসাইনমেন্ট পার্শেল নম্বর এম জি 28667092			
PLACE OF BOOKING	DATE OF DELIVERY	NATURE OF GOODS	PCS	WT	CONSIGNMENT DECLARED VALUE	PLACE OF BOOKING	PLACE OF DELIVERY
	15/03/16						
FROM	TO		Tel		CHARGES		ACKNOWLEDGEMENT RECEIVED THE ABOVE MENTIONED CONSIGNMENT IN PERFECT AND GOOD CONDITION FROM SUNDARBAN COURIER SERVICE (PVT.) LTD. DELIVERED BY RECEIVED BY DATE TIME BRANCH
Md. Anwar Hossain	Sherz Ali Vile		073268811		SERVICE CHARGES VOLUMETRIC CHARGES DELIVERY CHARGE OTHER CHARGES TOTAL CHARGES		
04	Noviragar		073268811		CASH 8852941		
	Tel: Nat. Nazaryans						
প্রেরক এখানে নিশ্চিত করিতে যে, উল্লিখিত অর্ডারটি সঠিক এবং উপর পূরণ্য মুদ্রিত পত্র সংশ্লিষ্ট মাল পরিবহন ব্যবস্থার নথি। THE SHIPPER HEREBY CERTIFIES THAT ABOVE PARTICULARS ARE CORRECT AND AGREE THAT THE GOODS SHALL BE CARRIED UPON THE CONDITIONS REFERRED TO IN THE REVERSE HEREOF.				মালমাল সম্পূর্ণ ভাল অবস্থায় বুঝিয়া পাইলাম CONSIGNMENT RECEIVED IN GOOD CONDITION		মালমাল সম্পূর্ণ ভাল অবস্থায় বুঝিয়া পাইলাম CONSIGNMENT RECEIVED IN GOOD CONDITION	
SIGNATURE OF BOOKING OFFICER		DELIVERY INSTRUCTION		DELIVERY INFORMATION		POD INFORMATION	
[Signature]				NAME DATE TIME		[Signature]	
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	১০৪		০৭৩২৬৮৮১		CASH ৪৪৫২৯৪১		
	১০৪		০৭৩২৬৮৮১				
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[Signature]				NAME DATE TIME		[Signature]	
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01 23

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PLACE OF BOOKING	DATE	MATERIALS	PCS	WT.	TAKA	PLACE OF DELIVERY
	15-03-16				20/-	
TO Charisma, World University of Bangladesh, Dhanmoadi, Dhaka					ACKNOWLEDGEMENT RECEIVED THE ABOVE MENTIONED CONSIGNMENT IN PERFECT AND GOOD CONDITION FROM SUNDARBAN COURIER SERVICE (PVT.) LTD.	
FROM Engr. Md. Anowar Nikunja-2					DELIVERED BY SCS নিউজ DATE: 8952941 TIME: 12:00 PM	
RECEIVERS SIGN & SEAL					BRANCH	
					CONSIGNMENT RECEIVED IN GOOD CONDITION	
					SEAL & NAME OF CC-SIGNEE POD INFORMATION	

01 23

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PLACE OF BOOKING	DATE	MATERIALS	PCS	WT.	TAKA	PLACE OF DELIVERY
	15-03-16				20/-	
TO Charisma, Victoria University of Bangladesh, Pantua Path, Dhaka					ACKNOWLEDGEMENT RECEIVED THE ABOVE MENTIONED CONSIGNMENT IN PERFECT AND GOOD CONDITION FROM SUNDARBAN COURIER SERVICE (PVT.) LTD.	
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					CONSIGNMENT RECEIVED IN GOOD CONDITION	
					SEAL & NAME OF CC-SIGNEE POD INFORMATION	

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PLACE OF BOOKING	DATE	NATURE OF GOODS	PCS	WT.	TAKA	PLACE OF BOOKING	PLACE OF DELIVERY
	15-03-16				20K		
TO Chairman, University of South Asia Baranai, Dhaka						ACKNOWLEDGEMENT RECEIVED THE ABOVE MENTIONED CONSIGNMENT IN PERFECT AND GOOD CONDITION FROM SUNDARBAN COURIER SERVICE (PVT.) LTD. DELIVERED BY: _____ RECEIVED BY: SCS DATE: 15/03/2022 8952941 (BRANCH)	
FROM Engr. Md. Anowar						RECEIVED IN GOOD CONDITION	
TEL: _____						SEAL & NAME OF CONSIGNEE POD INFORMATION: _____	
RECEIVERS SIGN & SEAL						_____	

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PLACE OF BOOKING	DATE	NATURE OF GOODS	PCS	WT.	TAKA	PLACE OF BOOKING	PLACE OF DELIVERY
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 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing &
 process, color engg), applied law & criminology
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 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
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Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
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গুণমান সেন্সিটিভিভি বাস, স্টেংকন, ব্রিগকোম, অ্যান্টি বাস, কুম-কলেজ
 স্যান্ড, সেন্সিটিভ, সেন্সি, হাফা, প-কলেজী ও সূচনা লিডার লেদা পুত্র।
 রাজস্বিক প্রিট সেক্টর, নিচ ডলা। ফোনন # ৩০, নিতুন-২, শিলালেক, ঢাকা-১২২৯।
 মোবাইল : ০১৭২১-১৪২৯৯৯, ০১৬৭৬-৯০১০৮৮

নং: *১০০০০০০০*
 নাম: *[Signature]*

ঠিকানা: *[Signature]*

ক্রমা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	মূল্য	টাকা
<i>১</i>	<i>max - [Signature]</i>	<i>২</i>	<i>২০০০</i>	<i>৪০০০</i>

কথার: *[Signature]*

ওয়ারেন্ট যুক্ত মাল কোম্পানি থাকলে পাবেন।
 জেতার স্বাক্ষর **বিঃদ্রঃ বিক্রিত মাল ফেরৎ লভ্য হয় না।** বিক্রোতার স্বাক্ষর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
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তারিখ-15-03-16

মো: জাহিদ হাজার
 কোম্পা এন্ট্রিস্টান মার্কেট জাহিদ হাজার

প্রক্ষেপ: গিলঙ্কেত থেকে আমতলা → ২০ F
 বাজর থেকে কৌচক → ২০ F
 কৌচক থেকে গিলঙ্কেত → ২০ F
 টোটাল ৬০ F

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 [Signature]
 16/03/16

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তারিখ 16-03-16

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 গুল কান থেকে ফার্মেন্টে → ২০
 ফার্মেন্টে থেকে গিলঙ্কেত → ২০
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19-03-16

কো: জাহিদ হাভান
 পোষ্ট: এচিফটার হারভের চাইল্ডার
 প্রাপ্য: অিলঙ্কোথ থেকে বনামী → ২৫৮
 বনামী থেকে কচুঙ্কোথ → ১০৮
 মিরপুর থেকে অিলঙ্কোথ → ২০৮
 মোট ৫০৮

Approved By

 19/03/16

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 To: ১১

Consignee: **৩৯৮৬৭**
 Consignee: Tel: ৩৯৮৬৭

Date: ১৯/৩/১৬

Shipper: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

Destination: Dhaka
 Declared Value: ৩৯৮৬৭
 POS: KG, CM

Service Charge: ২০৮

Total: ২০৮

SHIPPER'S SIGNATURE:

SHIPPER'S ADDRESS: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S PHONE: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S TEL: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S FAX: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S E-MAIL: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S BUSINESS: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S COUNTRY: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S CITY: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S STATE: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S ZIP CODE: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S TAX ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S VAT ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S PAN ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

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SHIPPER'S UEN ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S EIN ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S GST ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S HSN ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

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SHIPPER'S FSSAI ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S BIS ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S ISI ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S BIR ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S COC ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S NABL ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S ISO 9001 ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S ISO 14001 ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S ISO 27001 ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S ISO 45001 ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S ISO 50001 ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S ISO 26000 ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

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SHIPPER'S ISO 24700 ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S ISO 24800 ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S ISO 24900 ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

SHIPPER'S ISO 25000 ID: **১৯৯৬৭৩১২**

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 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
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 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
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 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 21/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: চাইল্ডম্যান
 Purpose: Purcharing chemical
 Description:

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 21/03/16

বিল -

২১-০৩-১৬

কো: জাহিদুজ্জামান
 কোষ: এচিআন মার্কেট ডাইজার
 প্রাপ্য: ঝিলকোত থেকে জোয়াখালি → ২০₹
 জোয়াখালি থেকে অদর ঘাট → ২০₹
 অদর ঘাট থেকে → ২৬₹
 জিম্মিরা থেকে পারকোমুদুরী (Rickshaw) → ৬৫
 কাঙ্গী গাজ থেকে জিম্মিরা → ৬০
 অদর ঘাট থেকে ঝিলকোত → ২০
 মোট ১৯১

APPROVED BY
 [Signature]
 21/03/16

RECEIVED BY
 [Signature]
 21-03-16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill Date: 21/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman
 Purpose: TIN Identification Number for Business Account

Description:

TIN (Personal) for Bank Account in Rupali Bank → 1500f

Approved & Received By
 A.H.
 21/03/16

Total → 1500f

Bill Date: 22/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman
 Purpose: office draw

Description:

4 Set draw for 02 person → 10.000f

Approved & Received By
 A.H.
 22/03/16

10.000f

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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1

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PLACE OF BOOKING: 22/03/16 DATE: 22/03/16 PLACE OF DELIVERY: DATIVE/030003 PCS WT		CONSIGNMENT DECLARED VALUE: 28685819		PLACE OF BOOKING: PLACE OF DELIVERY:	
FROM ডাঃ আনোয়ার হোসেন বিজ্ঞান কেন্দ্র-২ ০১৭৩২৬৪১ ০৪		TO ৩৭৩২৫৫ ০১১০ ০১৭৩২৬৪১ ০৪		ACKNOWLEDGEMENT RECEIVED THE ABOVE MENTIONED CONSIGNMENT IN PERFECT AND GOOD CONDITION FROM SUNARBAN COURIER SERVICE (PVT.) LTD. DELIVERED BY: [Signature] RECEIVED BY: [Signature] SEAL & SIGNATURE OF CONSIGNEE: [Signature] SEAL & SIGNATURE OF CONSIGNEE: [Signature]	
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বিল ২২-০৩-১৬

স্রো: ডাঃ আনোয়ার হোসেন

স্রো: বিজ্ঞান কেন্দ্র-২ থেকে মিরপুর ২০

মিরপুর ২০ থেকে বিজ্ঞান কেন্দ্র-২

মিরপুর ২০ থেকে বিজ্ঞান কেন্দ্র-২ → ৫০ F

বিজ্ঞান কেন্দ্র-২ থেকে মিরপুর ২০ → ২০ F

মিরপুর ২০ থেকে বিজ্ঞান কেন্দ্র-২ → ৬০

মোট ১৩০

APPROVED BY [Signature] 22/03/16

Receive BY [Signature] 23-03-16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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বিল ২৩/০৩/১৬

কো: জাহিদ হোসেন

পোস্ট: অসিস্ট্যান্ট মার্চ্যান্ডাইজার.

প্রার্থ্য: স্থানীয় থেকে অর্ডার গ্রহণ → ৫০ F.

আজাদকোট থেকে স্থানীয় → ১০ F.

মোট ৭০

APPROVED BY *AS* ২৩/০৩/১৬

RECEIVED BY *[Signature]* ২৪/০৩/১৬

bill Date 24/03/16

Md: Jahid Hossain

post Assistant Merchandiser

PURPOSE: স্থানীয় থেকে রানপুরা → ২০ F

বাছা থেকে স্থানীয় → ১০ F

মোট ৩০

APPROVED BY *AS* ২৪/০৩/১৬

RECEIVED BY *[Signature]* ২৭/০৩/১৬

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ক্যাশ মেমো

১৬৫

তারিখ ২৭/৩/২০২৫

নাম

ঠিকানা

ক্র.সং.	মালের বিবরণ	সাইজ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
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টাকার কথায়

বিক্রয়কারী

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রয়কারী

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

বিঃদ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল ফেরৎ লওয়া হয় না।

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

27/08/16

Md. Jahid Hossain

past Assitan Merchanduser

Description

খিলকোম্ব থেকে অকবায়ার →
 কৌচাক থেকে খিলকোম্ব ←

১৫ F
 20
 ———
 35

Approved By

A.H.
 27/08/16

Received By

 27/08/16

Bill

27/08/16

Md. Jahid Hossain

past Assitan Merchanduser

Description

খিলকোম্ব থেকে অকবায়ার →
 কৌচাক থেকে খিলকোম্ব ←

১৫ F
 20
 ———
 35

Approved By

A.H.
 27/08/16

Received By

 27/08/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

bill 29/03/16

Md: Jahid Hossain

Description

স্বত্বস্বত্বিকি → ২০F

Approved by

29/03/16

Receivabley

29/03/16

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Bill

37/08/16
29/03/16

Md. Jahid Hossain
 post Assistan Merchandiser

Description

ফিলটেক্স থেকে কাপাসান	→	20 F
কাপাসান থেকে অর্জিবিল	→	2 F
অর্জিবিল থেকে সার্ভিসেট	→	20 F
অর্জিবিল থেকে ফিলটেক্স	→	20 F
		80

৳৮০

Approved By
 AI
 29/03/16

Receive By
 (Signature)
 29/03/16

Bill

Date: 30/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chair man
 Purpose: Office Entertainment

Description:

Lunch Bill	→	450f
		450f

Total → 450f

Approved By
 AI
 30/03/16

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Md. Jahid Hossain 31/03/16
 post Assistant Merchandiser
 Description
 ডিলভার্ড থেকে মিরপুর ২০ → ৩০F
 মিরপুর থেকে ফার্মসিটি → ১৬F
 ফার্মসিটি থেকে মিরপুর ২ → ২০F
 মিরপুর থেকে ডিলভার্ড → ৩০F
 মোট ১০৬F
 Approved By: [Signature] 31/03/16
 Receive By: [Signature] 30/03/16

Bill Date: 31/03/16
 Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman
 Purpose: Salary
 Description:
 Salary of March-16 → 50.000F
 Approved & Received By: [Signature] 31/03/16
 Total → 50.000F

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

Date: 31/03/16

Name : Mrs. Jahid Hameen
 Post : Assistant Merchandiser
 Purpose : Office salary
 Description :

Salary of March → 8000/-

Approved
 &
 A. Abd
 31/03/16

Received By
 A. Abd
 31/03/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill Date: 31/03/26

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
Post: Chairman

Purpose: Fee show room rental dealing.

Description:
 Paving to market office → 2000f

Total → 2000f

Approved & Received By
 [Signature]
 31/03/26

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Office Expenditure, April - 2016

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Expenditure of April

Description:

Office Salary → 60,000f

Outlet Advance → 50,000f

Outlet Goodn → 53230f

Conveyance → 1894f

Office Entertainment → 5280f

Newspaper → 310f

Internet Bill → 500f

Mobile Bill → 2000f

House rent → 12000f

Miscellaneous → 2305f

Bank → 650f

Stamp → 330f

Show room Decoration → 20095f

Total → 208594f

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02/04/16

Md. Jahid Hossain
 Post Assistant Merchandiser

Description
 নাগুয়াবিল _____
 (Office Entertainment amount) ₹90F
 মো 490F

Approved By
 [Signature]
 01/04/16

02/04/16

কাজের ব্যয়
 ০১৭১২১১৪৯৪

* কাজের ব্যয়
 ০১৭১২১১৪৯৪

০১৭১২১১৪৯৪

০১৭১২১১৪৯৪

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02/04/16

Mr. Zahid Hossain
 Post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

- খিলছোক থেকে মিরপুর ২ →
- মিরপুর থেকে কার্জনগেট →
- বান্দাপুরা থেকে খিলছোক →

30 F
 15 F
 15 F
 মোট 60 F

Approved By

 02/04/16

Received By

 02/03/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
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কাশ মেমো

রেনেসাঁ স্টেশনারী এন্ড লাইব্রেরী

এখানে ফুল, কলম ও অফিসিয়াল স্টেশনারী, কম্পিউটার সামগ্রী, বই-পাতা, কলম ও পেনসিল খুচরা ও পাইকারী
 মূল্যে বিক্রয় ও অর্ডার সরবরাহ করা হয় এবং ফটোকপি, স্পাইরাল/বুক বন্ডিং, লেমিনেটিং ও প্রিন্ট করা হয়।
 রাজস্বিক ট্রেড সেক্টর, দোকান নং-১১বি/সি (নীচতলা, পশ্চিম গেইট সংলগ্ন), নিকুঞ্জ-২, হিজলেক্ট, ঢাকা-১২২৯

নং **1304** মোবাইল : ০১৯১২-২২৬০৫০ তারিখ **০৬/০৪/২০১৬**

নাম			
ঠিকানা			
বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
স্টেশনারী	৬	২২০	১৩২০
		মোট-	১৩২০

টাকা কথায় :

ক্রমিক স্বাক্ষর বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

কেন্দ্রীয়ভাবে শীতাতপ নিয়ন্ত্রিত

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

04/04/16

Md. Zahid Hossain

Post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

শ্রিলঙ্কাত থেকে আমদানি →

10 F

স্বাদেশীয় থেকে আমদানি →

10 F

মোট 20 F

Approved By

04/04/16

Received By

05/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
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 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
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 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

05/04/16
05/04/16

past chairman

Descriptive

- খিলকোত থেকে বহুবাজার →
- বহুবাজার থেকে খিলকোত →
- খিলকোত থেকে মনবাজার →
- মোমামালি থেকে খিলকোত →

৬০ F
২৭০ F
৩০ F
১০ F
মোট ৩৬০ F

Approved by

 06/04/16

Recd by

 06/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

বিস্মিল্লাহির রাহমানির রাহিম কাশ মেমো

বাবলী ও মায়ের দোয়া ও আল্লার দান

BABLI & MAYER DOYA & ALLARDAN

এখানে হেংগার, বডি, সুতা ইত্যাদি পাওয়া যায়।

মহানগর কমপ্লেক্স, ২য় তলা
দোকান নং-১০৮/১১০/১১২
ফুলবাড়ীয়া, শাহবাগ, ঢাকা-১০০০।

বঙ্গবাজার কমপ্লেক্স ব্যবসায়ী সমিতি
দোকান নং-২৯৭/২৯৮, নীচ তলা
ফুলবাড়ীয়া, শাহবাগ, ঢাকা-১০০০।

☎ 04475-985756
 ☎ 04475-985754
 ☎ 04475-985988
 ☎ 01799-597860
 ☎ 01857-751469
 ☎ 01679-100862

নং: 2214 প্রোগ্রাম মোঃ বাবুল তারিখ: ০৫/০৪/২৬

নাম: রাসুল হোসেন সৈয়দ

ঠিকানা: শাহবাগ, ঢাকা

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
১	২০ গাউন এক্সপোজ	৫৪০	১৫	৮১০০
২	২০ গাউন এক্সপোজ	৬৬০	৬	৩৯৬০
৩	২০ গাউন এক্সপোজ	২৭০	৫২	১৪০৪
৪	এক্সপোজ/নাইলন/সি/১০০	২০	৩১	৬২০
৫	২০ গাউন এক্সপোজ	২০	২৫	৫০০
৬	২০ গাউন এক্সপোজ	২০	২৫	৫০০
৭	২০ গাউন এক্সপোজ	২০	২৫	৫০০
৮				২৫০০
৯			⊖	০
১০				২৫০০
১১				
১২				
১৩				
১৪				
১৫				
১৬				
১৭				
১৮				
১৯				
২০			মোট-	১৬০০০

তোমাদের মধ্যে শ্রেষ্ঠ, যে কোরআন নিজে শিখা করে এবং অপরকে শিখা দেয়।
 সততা ব্যবসার মূলধন
 বিঃদ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল ফেরৎ লওয়া হয় না।

ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর- বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর-

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

বিস্মিত্যাহির রাহমানির হাফিজ

জিহাদ ইঞ্জিনিয়ারিং ওয়ার্কস

এখানে সর্বশ্রকার আলমারী, দরজা, জানালা, প্রীল
 কন্সাপসেবল গেইট, রোলিং সার্টার ইত্যাদি তৈরী ও
 এস.এস.এর কাজ সরবরাহ করা হয়।

৭১১, টমী ডাইজারশন রোড, মগবাজার রেলগেট, ঢাকা-১২১৭
 মোবাইল : ০১৭১৬-৮০১৭৩৮, ০১৯৪৭-১৬৬৮৭১

সূত্র

তারিখ : ০৫-০৪-২০১৬

ফোন নম্বর (০৭-০৪-২০১৬) বিবেচনা

৫ S.S 3/4 কাছির ইন্ডোর ইন্টারনাল স্ক্রী = ২৫০০ টি
 স্ক্রী = ২০০০ টি
 বার্ডি বিল্ডিং ৬-০০৮১৩১৩১

০৫-০৪-২০১৬

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

~~06/04/16~~

06/04/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

past chairman

Description

শিল্পক্ষেত্র থেকে অদ্বৈগ্যে →

৮০ F

অদ্বৈগ্যে থেকে শিল্পক্ষেত্র →

৭০ F

ব্যয় বিতরণ →

১০ F

মোট 150 F

Approved By

 06/04/16

Receb By

 06/04/16

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ক্যাশ মেমো ০১৯৪২৩৩৮১১৭
০১৮৬৭৮২০৩৯৯

রোমান এন্টারপ্রাইজ

নং ৬৩৪ এখানে স্কাবার টায় (সিল), সাইনবোর্ড ও ব্যানারসহ ব্যবসায় পিচবোর্ড কাজ করা হয়।
 টাংগাইল প্রাঙ্গণ, মোকাম নং-২১, বিলকোত, ঢাকা-১২২৯।

তারিখ ৯/৪/১৫ তারিখ জা. ১৬/৪/১৫

নাম	পরিমাণ	বিবরণ	দর	টাকা
সাইন বোর্ড/ব্যানার	১	৪৪৫৫	৩৭	১৩০০
ডিজিটাল প্রিন্ট				
ডিজিটিং কার্ড				
ক্যাশ মেমো/বিল				
পত্রিকায় বিজ্ঞাপন				
			মোট	১৩০০
			অগ্রীম	১২০০
			বাকী	১০০

৯/৪/১৫ তারিখ

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

08/04/16

Name Md. Anowar Hossain

Post chairman

Description-

শ্রিলঙ্কায় থেকে আসলনা →

30 F

আসলনা থেকে শ্রিলঙ্কায় →

30 F

60 F

স্বাক্ষর

Approved By & Received By

08/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
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MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
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PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
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 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
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 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
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 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

সোনাল ৩১৯১৩ ৫৭২৫০৬

মায়ের দোয়া ইঞ্জিনিয়ারিং ওয়ার্কস

MAER DOYA ENGINEERING WORKS

শ্রেষ্ঠ মোঃ ফারুক হোসেন

এখানে বাংলাদেশের গার্মেন্টস, গোয়াং শ্রমজা, জামানা, কল্যাণসিকার পেট, সলিটর পেট, স্টিল আলমারী
 টার্ট এর যন্ত্র, চেয়ার টেবিল সহ স্টীলের ব্যবহার্য মাশিনার তৈরী ও সংস্কার করা হয়।
 ফোন-৩১, ফ্যাক্স-৫/১৭৮, নিতুঞ্জ-৩২, বিলাফেজ, টানগাজা, ঢাকা-১২২/৯।

Bill No: **163** তারিখ: **২০২১-০৪-২০২১**

নাম:
 ঠিকানা:

ক্র.সং	বিবরণ	বর্ধিত	দর	টাকা
০১	হেডার ও স্ট্রাকচার	-	-	৩২০/-
				৩২০/-
মোট				৩২০/-

স্বাক্ষর

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Corporate Office : House # 1/A, Road # 12, Floor # 2nd
Nikunja-2, Dhaka-1229 Phone : 8962896, 7911085
Cell : 01619090000, 01198090000, www.myadvanceit.net

2972

DATE: 1 2 0 4 2 0 1 6
D D M M Y Y Y Y

Thanks with ait. Anwar

The Sum of Taka _____ TK

5000

Month of April-16 Instalation Charge _____

- Internet Section Software Section Domain Registration Web Hosting Training Section
 Nikunja Office Uttara Office

Monir
Authorized Signature

- * প্রতিস্থাপন চার্জ অন্তর্ভুক্তযোগ্য
- * প্রতি মাসের ৫ তারিখের মধ্যে এই মাসের বিল পরিশোধ করতে হবে।
- * কোনোটি বদল করতে হলে অবশ্যই ১ (এক) মাস পূর্বে জানাতে হবে।

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BEST EXCHANGE
 100% Export Quality Knit & Woven Fabric Suppliers
 Grewal City, Nollani, Chowrasia, Joydebpur, Gazipur
 Cell No. : +88-01737221855, +88-01916425737

Bill No. **120** Date: 11.04.16

Name of Factory: BD Fashion Ltd
 Address: Kulikhat, Dhaka

Sl. No.	Description	Challan No.	Quantity	Rate	Taka
(*)	Polo-shirt		27 pcs	120	= 3240/-
(*)	P-shirt		36 pcs	40	= 1440/-
					= 4680/-
	Polo shirt (Amber)		21 pcs		4300
					8780/-

Taka (in words)

FOR : BEST EXCHANGE

 Authorised by

Store In-Charge Received by Accountant

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Bill

11/04/16

Md. Zahid Hossain

post Assistant merchandiser

Description

- খিলকোত থেকে জালনা →
- জালনা থেকে খিলকোত →
- গাজীপুরা থেকে জালনা →
- ব্যু বিক্রয় →

30 F
 60 F
 20 F
 10 F

 120

স্বাক্ষর

Receb By

11/04/16

Approved By

 11/04/16

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আনোয়ার হোসাইন ডিফেন্স স্টাডিজ ফুন্ডেড

কম্পিউটার সার্ভিসিং, কম্পিউটার কন্সাল্টাং, ইন্টারনেট, ফান্ডিং, ইন্ডিয়া, ডিজিটেল, সেমিনারিং, ফটোগ্রাফি,
 ডেপন্ডেন্সি, সেন্সর সাফটওয়্যার। হোত নং-১০, কাজী নং-২৩, কিশোর-২, কিশোরগঞ্জ, ঢাকা-১২২৯।

ক্রমিক নং: **ANOWAR HOSSAIN** তারিখ: **২ ১৯/০৩/১৬**

নাম: **ANOWAR HOSSAIN**

ঠিকানা: _____

ক্রমিক নং	মালের বিবরণ	দর	পরিমাণ	টাকা
	Ted	60	1	

মোট টাকা = **60**

টাকা (কথায়) _____

ক্রমিক নং: _____ বিক্রয়কার সাফটওয়্যার

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B211

12/04/16

Md. Zahid Hossain

post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

খিলছোত থেকে বনানী	→	০৫F
বনানী থেকে খিলছোত	→	০৫F
		<u>১০</u>

Approved By

 12/04/16

Received By

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01/23

Bill

13/04/16

Md Zahid Hossain

Post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

ডিলিভারি থেকে উল্লেখ্য লোড	→	20 F
উল্লেখ্য থেকে টাকা জরিফ	→	25 F
		25 F
৳ বিক্রি	→	20 F
হাউজ বিল্ডিং থেকে আলপাড়া	→	20 F
৳ বিক্রি	→	20 F
হাউজ বিল্ডিং থেকে ডিলিভারি	→	20 F
৳ বিক্রি	→	20 F
		10
		2140

Approved ৳

13/04/16

Received by
 (20)

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

14/04/16
13/04/16

Md. Zahid Hossain

Post: Assistant Merchandiser

Description -

বিক্রাজাড়া	→	60 F 150 F
দোকানের চাঁদা	→	70 F
কার্টন	→	<u>Total = 280 F</u>

Received by

13/04/16

Approved By

13/04/16

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 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

BILL

13/04/16

Md. Zahid Hossain
 Post Assistant Merchandiser

Description:

ৱাভে ————— ৪১০
 ৩৫৬ ————— ৪১০

APPROVED BY

 10/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

14/04/16

Md. Jahid Hossain

Post: Assistant Merchandiser

Description

বিক্রয় কাজ

70 F

দোকানের চাঁদা

50 F

মু্য বিক্রা

১০ F
 মোট ২০ F

Approved By

[Signature]
 14/04/16

Received By

[Signature]

14/04/16

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ক্যাশ মেমো

মেসার্স মাসুদ ইলেকট্রিক এন্ড হার্ডওয়্যার

যাবতীয় ইলেকট্রিক, হার্ডওয়্যার মস্বাদি পাইকারী ও খুচরা
 বিক্রয় এবং সরবরাহকারী।

শ্রোঃ আব্দুল আহাদ

দোকান নং-২১, বেইজমেন্ট, রাজউক ট্রেড সেন্টার,
 নিকুঞ্জ-২, খিলক্ষেত, ঢাকা। মোবাইল : ০১১৯৯-৭৯০৯৯১

ক্রমিক নং- ৬৬১ তারিখঃ ০৭/০৪/২২

নাম :
 ঠিকানাঃ

পরিমাণ	বিবরণ	দর	টাকা
	গুলা - AMBR ৫০ম	২৫০	২৫০৬
	শালু - ৫০ম		২৫০৭
		মোট=	৫০১৩

বিঃ দ্রঃ বিক্রিত মাল ক্ষেত্র বা বদলানো হয় না।

ক্রোতার স্বাক্ষর বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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01

Guest Memo

Phone : 9676679
Mobile : 01677-188819
: 01817-660795

ঢাকা স্টেশনারী Dhaka Stationery

90, New Super Market (Uttor) D-Block
Ground Floor, Dhaka-1205.

No. 4752

Date: ০৬/৪/২১

Name :

Address :

Qty	Description	Rate	Taka
০১ পিস	২০০০০০ (০০০০)	০০০০	০০০০
০২ "	০০০০০০	০০০০	০০০০
০২ "	০০০০০০	০০০০	০০০০
		Total-	০০০০

Goods once delivered will not be taken back.

Signature

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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 17/04/26

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: show room decoration & related

Description:

Show room coloring	→	2200f
Electrical wiring	→	1200f
Hanger attaching	→	1200f
Electrical wire purchasing	→	1500f
conveyance	→	50f
		<hr/>
		Total → 6150f

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 17/04/26

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bell

17/04/16

Md. Jahid Hossain

post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

খিলকাত থেকে বেলগোটে	→	10 F
		50 F
বেলগোটে থেকে খিলকাত	→	10 F
By বিক্রা	→	৳৮০
		<u>৳০ F</u>

APPROVED BY

 17/04/16

Received BY

 17/04/16

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"বিস্মিতকারীকর মাংসাদির মাংসে"

পাওয়ার হাউজ

POWER HOUSE

for electric & kitchen needs

এখানে সবল এককল ব্যান, অর্জার লাইট, প্রায়ের দুলাসহ আরও
 ইলেকট্রিক মালামাল ও প্রাচীর মাংসী কিনা করা হক।
 নাকী # ০০, রোড # ১২, বিকুল-২, ঢাকা-১২২৯।

ভাউচার

নাম : শ্রীমতী অমলতা হোসেন তারিখ : ১৪/০৪/১৬

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	টাকা
*	বৈদ্যুতিক অর্জার লাইট	৩৫০/-
*	বিকুল কো স্ট্রিং	১৫০/-
*	বৈদ্যুতিক স্ট্রিং	২২০/-
*	স্ট্রিং	২৫/-
*	স্ট্রিং	২৩০/-
*	RFL স্ট্রিং	২৪০/-
*	কম্পিউটার	৩০/-
মোট		১৪৩০/-

ধন্যবাদ আবার আশ্রয়

ক্রমিক নং

স্বাক্ষর
বিস্মিতকারীকর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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পাওয়ার হাউজ
POWER HOUSE
 for electric & kitchen needs

এখানে সবল প্রকার বয়ান, চার্জার লাইট, প্যাম্পের টুলসহ ব্যবহার্য ইলেকট্রিক মালামাল ও গ্রাটিক সামগ্রী বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 বাড়ী # ৫০, রোড # ১২, নিতুল-২, ঢাকা-১২২৯।

ফোন : ০২-৫৬০৮৩০
 মোব : ০১৭১২-৮০৮৩০৫

ভাউচার

নাম : তারিখ : ২৪/৪/২০২৬

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	টাকা
৫	হোটেল এনালজী ৪৫W ২P	৫০০/=
<p>paid</p> <p>২৪/৪/২০২৬</p>		
	মোট-	৫০০/=

ধন্যবাদ আবার আশ্রয়।

ক্রয়কার স্বাক্ষর

৫/৩/২৬
 বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
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 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur,
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 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

"বিশ্বকিছিকি মাংসখোরি মাংসি"
পাওয়ার হাউস
POWER HOUSE
 for electric & kitchen needs
 এখানে সকল ধরনের ফ্যান, চার্জ এ লাইট, গ্যাসের সুলাপহ যন্ত্রাদি
 ইলেকট্রিক মলামাল ও প্রাক্টিক সামগ্রী বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 বাড়ি # ৫০, রোড # ১২, নিউমল-২, ঢাকা-১২২৯।
ভাউচার

নাম : তারিখ : ২৮/৪/২০

সংখ্যা	বিক্রয়	টাকা
*	সেটিনা এনার্জি ২০৫৫৫৪	২,৪০০/-
ওয়ারেন্টি গ্যারান্টি paid ২৮/৪/২০		
		মোট- ২,৪০০/-

ধন্যবাদ আবার অভিনন্দন :

ক্রয়ের স্বাক্ষর

স্বাক্ষর
 বিক্রয়কার স্বাক্ষর

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bell

18-04-16

Md. Jahid Hossain

Post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

জাহিদ হোসেন

30 F

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By বিয়া

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Received by

Approved By

AS

18/04/16

18/04/16

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ক্যাশ মেমো

বিডিটি রেস্টোরা

সকল প্রকার খাবার এর অর্ডার নেওয়া হয়।
 ১নং নীলক্ষেত সিটি কর্পোরেশন মার্কেট, ঢাকা-১২০৫
 মোবাইল: ০১৭৬৪-৬৯৪৭২১, ০১৮১৬-১৭৮৮৯১
 ০১৭২০-০০৭৭৯১, ০১৭২৩-৭৭৯৯১৩

নং- _____ তারিখ: ২০ ০৭ ১৬

নাম: **শ্রী. আনওয়ার হোসাইন**

ঠিকানা: _____

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
	Lunch-০২ খিচরী			১৫০৳
ধন্যবাদ আবার আসবেন			মোট	১৫০৳

২০/০৭/১৬
 জেতার স্বাক্ষর

 বিক্রতার স্বাক্ষর

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11 | 13

শফিক : ০১৯১৭-২১২৯২২
 : ০১৬৭১-৭১৪৩৪৪
 রফিক : ০১৯৪১-৪৯০৬৪৮

আর, এস, পয়েন্ট

খোঃ মোঃ শফিকুল ইসলাম/রফিকুল ইসলাম
 সকল প্রকার পেঞ্জী প্রস্তুতকারক ও পাইকারী বিক্রেতা।

দোকান নং-ই-এস-২৯,৩০, মহানগর কমপ্লেক্স, ফনিব্ল রোড, ফুলবাড়ীয়া, শাহবাগ, ঢাকা-১০০০
 পূর্ব গোপাল নগর, বক্তাবলী, ফতুল্লা, নারায়ণগঞ্জ।

নং: **3044** তারিখ: **20/08/23**

নাম: _____
 ঠিকানা: _____

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
১	কম্বো	০৬	০০০	৭৬০/-
২	সইন	০৬	০০০	৬৯০/-
৩				২৪০/-
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মোট- _____

ক্রতর স্বাক্ষর **যে আল্লাহ কে পেল, সে সব পেল।** পক্ষে : আর, এস, পয়েন্ট

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Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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বিস্মিল্লাহির রাহমানির রাহিম মোবাইলঃ ০১৭৩৬-৮৫০৭৯১
 ক্যাশ মেমো : ০১৬৮৮-৯৪২৭০৪

কাওছার গার্মেন্টস
KAWSER GARMENTS

খোঁঃ- মোঃ মিজানুর রহমান

অত্যাধুনিক ডিজাইনের গেল্লি, শার্ট, গার্মেন্টস সামগ্রী পাইকারী বিক্রেতা।
 মহানগর কামারপুঞ্জ, দোকান নং-E-X-৩, ফুলবাড়ীয়া, শাহবাগ, ঢাকা-১০০০

নং- **920** তারিখ **20 8 20**

সংখ্যা	বালের বিবরণ	পিছ	দর	টাকা
১	নেলিডস জেনারেল	২০	৭০০	৭০০
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বিশেষঃ- বিক্রিত মাল ফেরৎ দেওয়া হবে না।

ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর সততাই ব্যবসার মূলধন বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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বিউটি প্যান্ট হাউজ
BEAUTY PANT HOUSE

কোম্পানি আইডি নং: ১৯২৭-০৯-০৬৭৪

এখানে প্রদর্শিত এই নমুনাগুলি কেবলমাত্র প্রদর্শনের জন্য এবং এগুলি কোনও প্রকারে বিক্রি করা হবে না।
 উৎস: ১. উৎস: ১.

নং: 439 তারিখ: ২০/১১/২০২৬

ক্র.সং	বস্ত্রের বিবরণ	মিটার	মূল্য	টাকার
১	১০০% কটন প্যান্ট	৩৫	২৫০	৮৭৫০
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১০০% কটন প্যান্ট

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, product analysis and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com, s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 5 March 2026.

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 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
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 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

মাস মেমো
01977-99 86 11

মেসার্স নাঙ্গলকোট ট্রেডার্স
M/S. NANGALKOT TRADERS

মাথানে দেশী বিদেশী ব্রা পেন্টি ও ডাইজ পেন্টমেন্টের আমদানিকারক পাইকারী ও খুচর বিক্রেতা
৩৯৩/বি-২, পাউন্ডিয়া ব্যাংক মার্কেট (২য় অলা, ঢাকা-১২০৫)

২২৫

তারিখ: ২০/০৪/২৫

নাম: শ্রীমানঃ সত্যজিৎ কুমার সেনগুপ্ত

ঠিকানা: নিউমার্কেট-২, কুমিল্লা রোড

ক্রমিক	বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	মূল্য	টোল
০১	৫৯ বেনগোলি কালসহ	২ প	২৫০	২০০৫
০২				
০৩				
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১৬				
১৭				
১৮				
			মোট	২০০৫

বিঃদ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল সেবার লগনো হয় না।

ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর: বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর:

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

পারভেজ কালেকশন

পারভেজ কালেকশন
Parvaj Collection

এখানে সকল প্রকার
দেশী-বিদেশী শার্ট,
পাইকারী বিক্রয় করা হয়।

৯৭৭ নং বঙ্গবাজার কমপ্লেক্স
(২য় তলা) ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০

৭৫২ নং বঙ্গবাজার কমপ্লেক্স
ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০

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নং- **2594** তারিখ **২০/৪/২০২৪**

নাম **কালেকশন**

ঠিকানা **৬ বিষ্ণু**

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
১	শুক্রা A	৬	৪০০	৬২০০
২				
৩	কো A	৬	৪৫৬	৬৭০০
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২০				
২১				
২২				
			মোট টাকা	

বৈচিত্র্যময় ক্রিশিলা পোষাকের
এক অনন্য প্রতিষ্ঠান।

পাঁচ ওরাজ নামাজ আদায় করুন।

হাফেজা সখ পথে চলিলা জীবিকা নির্জন করে, তাহার পোনার প্রতি বন্ধু- অল-হাদীস

পারভেজ কালেকশন

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).
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 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission);
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 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
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বিস্মিল্লাহির রাহমানির রাহিম
ক্যাশ মেমো Mobile : 01724-911667
 01718-326321

জহুরুল গার্মেন্টস
Johurul garments

প্রোগ মোঃ ফরহাদ খান

এখানে প্যান্ট, কোর্ট, জিন্স, জ্যাকেট পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 ৭৪৩-৪৪, ১৮৬৭ বঙ্গবাজার কমপ্লেক্স বাবুসারী || পো-রুম ৪ ১৫০ বঙ্গবাজার কমপ্লেক্স
 সমিতি, ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০। (মহানগরী ২য় তলা) ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০।

নং- **৫২৬**

নাম **বাংলাদেশ (ডেপার্টমেন্ট -** তারিখ **২০/০৪/২০**

ঠিকানা **ফুলবাড়ীয়া - মিলুপাড়া - গুলশান**

নং	বিবরণ	শিট	দর	টাকা
১	বস শিট ফোঁস	৪৪	২৪০২	২০২০৫
২				
৩				
৪	স্ট্রাকচার	৪৪	৬৪০	৬০৪০৫
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মোট-

নিজে নামাজ পড়ুন অপরকে নামাজের জন্য ডাকুন।

ক্রমিক স্বাক্ষর বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Tel. . 01727545601
01749701270

ফাহিম ফ্যাশন
Fahim Fashion

এখানে উন্নত মানের দেশী-খ্রী পিছ পাইকারী বিক্রয়ের নির্ভরযোগ্য প্রতিষ্ঠান।
facebook.com/fahimfashion.com

৩৯৩/বি-৯০, নিউ চিশতিয়া মার্কেট, নীচ তলা (গাউছিয়া সংলগ্ন), ঢাকা-১২০৫।

নং 765 তারিখ ২৩ ০৪ ১৬

নাম বাহিম ফ্যাশন স্টোর এন্ড সার্ভিস

ঠিকানা ফাহিম ফ্যাশন

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	পিছ	দর	টাকা
১	জামা	০২	১০০০	২০০০
২	সামান্য পিন	০৬	১১০০	৬৬০০
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মোট

বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত লওয়া হয় না।

ক্রমিক নম্বর বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission);
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 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

ক্যাশ মেমো

দিপা ওড়না হাউজ

DEPA ORNA HOUSE

এখানে দেশী-বিদেশী ওড়না, কার্প এবং পাল পছন্দী ও খুন্দা বিক্রয়ের একমাত্র নির্ভরযোগ্য প্রতিষ্ঠান
 ৩৯৩/বি-১০০, নিউ চিশতিয়া মার্কেট (নীচতলা), গাইহিয়া সংলগ্ন, ঢাকা-১২০৫
 ফোনঃ ৯৬৭০৩৮৩, মোবাইলঃ ০১৭১৫-৯৫৫১১৩, ০১৮১৭-০৬১৮৫১

নং: 1565 তারিখ: ১০/৪/২৪

নাম: *ব্রাহ্মণদাস ঠিকানাঃ*

ঠিকানা:

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	পিস	দর	টাকা
০১	<i>ফোম খুন্দা</i>	০৬	২৫০	১৫০০
০২	<i>সাদা ওড়না</i>	০৬	৩৬০	২১৬০
০৩				
০৪				
০৫	<i>total</i>			৩৬৬০
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১০				

মোট- *৩৬৬০*

বিঃ দ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল ক্ষেত্রত লওয়া হয় না।

আগ্রাহ ব্যাবসাকে করেছেন হাদাল, হুদকে করেছেন হাদাম।

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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মোবাইল: ০১৯৯২৬-২১৩২৫৫
০১৭৩৪-০৪০৭০২

MB
DG

মা বাবার দোয়া গার্মেন্টস্

MAA BABAR DOA GARMENTS

প্রাঃ মোঃ আমজাদ হোসেন

এখানে আধুনিক ডিজাইনের গেঞ্জি প্রস্তুতকারক এবং পাইকারী বিক্রেতা।
দোকান নং-এ-১/২, মহানগর কমপ্লেক্স, ফুলবাড়িয়া, শাহবাগ, ঢাকা-১০০০

নং- **7239** (যে কোন তিজাইনের গেঞ্জি অর্ডার নেওয়া হয়) তারিখ **২০ ৪ ১৬**

নাম: _____
ঠিকানা: _____

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পিস	দর	টাকা	
১		২	১০০	৬৫০	
২	ব্লেজার T-shirt				
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২০/০৪/১৬

মোট-

সততাই ব্যবসার মূলধন
বিশ্ব দ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত লওয়া হয় না।
বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর "নিজে নামাজ পড়ুন এবং অপরকে পড়তে উৎসাহিত করুন" বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, product analysis and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com, s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 5 March 2026.

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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

ক্যাশ মেমো

নিস্ত

3 **থ্রী-স্টার গার্মেন্টস**
New Three Star Garments

প্রোগ্রাম কাজী মোঃ আরিফ

আরিফ : ০১৭১২-২১৩৬১৪
 আরমিন : ০১৮১১-৫২৪৫৫৪
 : ০১৬১১-০০০৭৭৪

এখানে আধুনিক শর্ট প্যান্ট ও বাচ্চাদের গেম্বলী সেট পাইকারী বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 দোকান নং-এ-৭৮/৭৯, মহানগর কমপ্লেক্স, (১০ ফুট গলি),
 ফুলবাড়ীয়া, শাহাবাগ, ঢাকা-১০০০।

নং- 1639 তারিখ 20/03/2021

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	সাইজ	পিছ	দর	টাকা
১	৬৮ নং প্যান্ট	৪২	২১	২১০	২০২০
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মোট-

পরিচালনায় : কাজী মোঃ আরমিন

ক্রমতার স্বাক্ষর "আল্লাহ ব্যবসাকে করেছেন হালাল, সুদ করেছে হারাম" বিক্রমতার স্বাক্ষর

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Bill

20/04/16

Md. Jahid Hossain

post Assistant Merchandiser

Description.

ফিল ড্রেশ থেকে সাউন্ড্রিয়া →	80F
সাউন্ড্রিয়া থেকে ড্রলিঙ্কান →	24F
ড্রলিঙ্কান থেকে ফিল ড্রেশ →	90F
৳ বিক্রয় →	10F
	<hr/>
	204F

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 20/04/16

Received by

 20/04/16

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

21-04-16

Md. Jahid Hossain
 past Assistant Merchandiser

Description

ছান ছাড়া	→	250F
বিশ্রা ছাড়া	→	60F
শালা বিল	→	50F
		<u>360F</u>
	মাকুনী →	15
Approved By		Received By
22/04/16	Total → 375F	21-04-16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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"কিন্তু কেবলই চাফোকাই থাকবে"

পাওয়ার হাউজ
POWER HOUSE
 for electric & kitchen needs

এখানে সকল শকার ফ্যান, চার্জার লাইট, গ্যাসের চুলা সহ যাবতীয় ইলেকট্রিক মালামাল ও প্রাচুর্য সামগ্রী বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 বাড়ী # ৫০, রোড # ১২, নিকুল-২, ঢাকা-১২২৯।

ভাউচার

নাম : তারিখ : ২২/৪/২০১৫

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	টাকা
	মুদ্রা কাগজ ১টি	১৪০
	২	
মোট-		১৪০

হুমায়দ আলীর স্বাক্ষরে।

ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

22-04-16

Md. ANOWAR HOSSAIN

po Chairman

Description

ফটোকপি কমিটি'র

নামাবলি

60F
 60F
 150
 210F

Approved By

AS
 22/04/16

স্বাক্ষর

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Bill

25-04-16

Md. Jahid Hossain

past Assistant Merchandiser

Description

প্রিলঙ্কার থেকে আর্ডার পূর → 05 F
 10 F

আর্ডার পূর থেকে প্রিলঙ্কার → 15
 মা 16

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 25/04/16

Received By

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Bill

26-04-16

Md. Jahid Hossain

post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

শিল্পক্ষেত্র সংক্রান্ত আনুসঙ্গিক পূর্ব → 05F

আনুসঙ্গিক পূর্ব সংক্রান্ত শিল্পক্ষেত্র → 05F
 (সিটি) 10F

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 26/04/16

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 26-04-16

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Bill

26-04-16

Md. Jahid Hossain

Post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

খিলছোত থেকে সীচাক	→	15 F
সীচাক ২২২০ কার্ডগেট	→	20 F
কার্ডগেট ২২২০ খিলছোত	→	15 F
	→	<u>40 F</u>

Approved by

26/04/16

Received by

26-04-16

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 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
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 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD
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 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
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 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

27-04-16

Purpose: Price Tag
 Description:

সবচেয়ে বেশি মিলে

→ 50 F
 (মোট) 50 F

Approved By

27/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

27-04-16

Mr Jahid Hossain

post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

প্রিন্টেড হইল বহুবাডার →	50 F
বহুবাডার হইল প্রিন্টেড →	50 F
প্রিন্টেড হইল আজমপুর →	05
আজমপুর থেকে প্রিন্টেড →	05
	10
	120

By বিক্রা

স্বাক্ষর

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27/04/16

27-04-16

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৩৫২ ৬০-৩১০-০০৬ Mob: 01710-306095
01942-367984

BHAI BHAI FASHION

সকল প্রকার এরগোপার্ট কেনারানিটি টি-শার্ট, নামেরটিস শোষক পাইকারী ও ফুরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 মোকদদ- ১৪৮৬, বঙ্গবাজার বঙ্গদেশের ব্যবসায়ী সংগঠিত, ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০।
 শো-রুম # ০২, যাহা'দে'স আরক'ড পরা। (প্রের পছন্দে প্রাশে), লেবন ৯- ০৪, নীচলা, ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০।

বিল/চানার

তারিখ: ১১/০৪/২৬

১৯৫৪

নাম:

ঠিকানা:

নং	বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাক
০৭	কাপড়	৫৫	২০০	১১০০

কাস্টমার:

সত্তা বাবদায় মূলধন

কর্তৃপক্ষ:

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Mob :01772-314915
: 01918-880718

প্রোগ মোঃ রুবেল

এখানে সকল প্রকার প্যান্ট পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
দোকান নং-১৪৪০, বঙ্গবাজার কমপ্লেক্স, ব্যাবসায়ী সমিতি
ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০।

নং-	916	তারিখ	১৭	০৫	১৬
নাম					
ঠিকানা					
সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পিছ	দর	টাকা	
১	১২/১১ ৩৮	৬৫	২০০	৬৬৫০	
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ক্রয়তার স্বাক্ষর

বিঃ দ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত লওয়া হয় না

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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ক্যাশ মেমো

Mob : 01711-821483
: 01672-414882

আল-মদিনা ফ্যাশন Al-Madina Fashion

প্রাঃ - মোঃ সাহশের আলী

এখানে সর্বপ্রকার এক্সপোর্টের প্যান্ট, ট্রাউজার ইত্যাদি পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।

স্টোর নং-১৪৬৪-৬৫, বঙ্গবাজার কমপ্লেক্স ব্যবসায়ী সমিতি

ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০।

নং-	663	তারিখ	২৭	০৪	২০২৬
নাম					
ঠিকানা					
সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পিছ	দর	টাকা	
১	বড় জিন্স	৫৭৭৫	২৫০	১৪৫০০	
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"নিজে নামাজ পড়ুন অপরকে নামাজ পড়তে বলুন।"

ক্রয়কার স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
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 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission);
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur,
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
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বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়ের রাহমানির রাহিম
ক্যাশ মেমো Mob. S : 01716-041394
 Z : 01712-964749
 সিয়াম গার্মেন্টস
Syam Garments
মোঃ শাহিন

এখানে সকল প্রকার এক্সপোর্ট কোয়ালিটি গার্মেন্টস পোষাক পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয়।
 ১৬১৮, বঙ্গবাজার কমপ্লেক্স বাবশালী সমিতি 1618, Bango bazar Complex Babshai Somiti
 (২য় তলা গুলিস্তান) ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০। (1st Floor, Gullistan) Fulbaria, Dhaka-1000.

নং- 980	তারিখ ২৯/৪/২০			
নাম	হাফিজুল ইসলাম চৌধুরী			
ঠিকানা	হাফিজুল ইসলাম চৌধুরী			
সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পিছ	দর	টাকা
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১৬			মোট-	

ক্রয়কার স্বাক্ষর বিঃ দ্রঃ বিক্রিত মাল ফেরৎ লওয়া হয় না। বিক্রয়কার স্বাক্ষর

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01927-765853
01726-270675

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SHIRMIN GARMENTS
Pro. Md. Shahin

All Kinds Of Jacket, Over Cot, Trauzar Jogging Set Wholesaler & Retailer.
 1679, Bangobazar Complex (1st Floor)

No **735** Gulisthan Market, Fulbaria, Dhaka-1000. Date **২৭ ০৭ ২০**

Name _____

Address _____

Sl No	Description	Pice	Rate	Amount
1	১১মি/১১মি	১.১৩	৪০১-	৬৫০/-
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14				
15			Total-	
16				

N.B : Goods Once Sold Cannot Be Taken Back

Receevir's Signature _____ For : Shirmin Garments

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

28/04/26

Name: Md. Jahid Hossain

Post: Asst. Merchandiser

Purpose: Salary

Description:

Approved By

[Signature]
28/04/26

Received By

[Signature]
21-05-16
Md. Jahid Hossain

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Date: 28/04/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: office cleaning

Description:

office cleaners → 2000f
 (April)

Approved
 &

Received By

AS

28/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
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Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post : chairman
 Purpose : Mobile Bill
 Description :

Date : 28/04/16

Mobile Bill → 2000₳

Approved
 &
 Received By
 Anowar
 28/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

28-04-16

Purpose: Prietag

Description

২০ টেক্সটাইল প্রকল্পে
 → ২০ F
 ← ২০

Approved By

AJ
 28/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman
 Purpose: Lunch Bill
 Description :

Date : 30/04/16

Lunch Bill of April → 4500f

4500f

Approved By
 &
 Received By
 A.H.
 30/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Date: 30/04/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Salary

Description:

Salary of Aptail → 50,000f

Approved
 &
 Received By
 A.H.
 30/04/16

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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 30/04/26

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman:
 Purpose: Outlet Advance
 Description:

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 30/04/26

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Office Expenditure . May-2016

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman

Purpose: Expenditure of May-16

Description :

- Office Salary → 52000₹
- Office rent → 10,000₹
- Conveyance → 1000₹
- Office Entertainment → 200₹
- Newspaper → 310₹
- Internet Bill → 500₹
- Mobile Bill → 1000₹
- Miscellaneous → 4310₹

Total → 69320₹

Approved
 &
 Received By

 31/05/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Date: 03/05/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman
 Purpose: office Entertainment
 Description:

office footing with buying
 house merchandiser

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 03/05/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Date: 04/05/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Hanger joining

Description:

Hanger joining charge → 250f

Approved

&

Received By

Abd
04/05/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

05/05/26

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Office cleaning
 Description:

Approved
 &
 Received By
 A.H.
 05/05/26

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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05/05/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : chairman

Purpose : Salary of May

Description :

Salary of May → 50,000₹

Approved
 &
 Received By

 05/05/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
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Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

5/05/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to marketing

Description:

Office to Barundhara → 20₹

Barundhara to office → 20₹

Total → 40₹

Approved
 &
 Received By

 05/05/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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AIT
Advance IT Technologies Limited
 6234

Nikunja Office: House -1/A, Road -12, 2nd Floor, Nikunja -2, Dhaka-1229, Ph: 01983300970 Cell: 01619090000, 01190090000
Uttara Office: R-14/B, H-1, 3rd floor, Sector-4, Uttara, Dhaka

DATE: 08 05 2016
 D D M M Y Y Y Y

Thanks with Cite Anowar

The Sum of Take _____ TK 500/-

Month of May-16 Installation Charge _____

Internet Section Software Section Domain Registration Web Hosting Training Section

Nikunja Office Uttara Office

[Signature]
 Authorized Signature

* প্রতিস্থাপন চার্জ অপেক্ষা করে
 * প্রতি মাসের ৫ তারিখের মধ্যে এটি মাসের বিদ্যমান পরিষেবা করতে হবে
 * সেবা টি বন্ধ করতে হলে অবশ্যই ১ (এক) মাস পূর্ব জানাতে হবে।

bKash : 01925773191

HOTEL ABAKASH (Residential) VR.NO 13/5/16
 654, O.R. Nizam Road, Chittagong. Date 13/5/16
 Tel: 633960, 28563120
 DEBIT/CREDIT ACCOUNT 2516

particulars	Taka	Ps
Received, Nine hundred	2900/-	
at 12th May/2016		
Room Rents only		
One days only		
TOTAL	2900/-	
Taka	v Nine hundred only.	

Receiver's Signature _____ Manager/Proprietor [Signature] 13/5/16 Cashier _____

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 15/05/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Mobile Bill

Description:

Mobile Bill —————→ 1000₳

Approved
 &
 Received By
 Anowar
 15/05/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

15/05/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Miscellaneous expenditure

Description:

Mobile Bill → 1000f

Milk → 450f

Coffee → 350f

Office Guest entertainment → 550f

Gift to shop owners → 230f
(By providing Brra)

Total → 2580f

Approved

&

Received By

15/05/16

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 16/05/26

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Chittagong for marketing

Description:

Fooding → 3000f
 (Wednesday evening to Friday evening)

Conveyance (Rickshaw) → 250f

Approved
 &
 Received By
 Ahsan
 16/05/26

Total → 1250f

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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ENA TRANSPORT (PVT.) LTD.

Ac/Non Ac exclusive coach service

Name : MR
Coach : [108-BRTC]
Departure Time : 01:15 PM
Seat Fare : TK. 480.00
Seats : [C1]
From : Chittagong
Boarding : Dampara Bus Point
Issued On : 13 May 2016

PNR : 57357A77E3F02
Journey Date : 13 May 2016
Reporting Time : 12:55 PM
Total Fare : TK. 480.00 x 2
= 960/-
To : Dhaka
Dropping :
Issued By : Mr. Nasir

যদি বসে বাসের টিকিট কিনুন সহজে, কল করুন Shohoz.com @ 16374
Serial # 16741 | Printed By: Mr. Nasir (operator)

আপনার হ্যান্ড লাগেজ অবশ্যই নিজ দায়িত্বে রাখবেন

অভিযোগ/পরামর্শঃ ০১৮-৬৯-৮০২৭৪০ চট্টগ্রাম, ০১৮-৬৯-৮০২৭২৭ ঢাকা

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Bill

Date: 29/05/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: office entertainment
 Description:

Entertainment for
 office Guest - 03 person → 1800

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 29/05/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

Date: 27/05/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose : Going to Tangail for marketing

Description :

Journey by bus & Rickshaw → 250₳

Fooding (Lunch) → 100₳

Approved
 &
 Received By
[Signature]
 27/05/16

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Bill

Date: 31/05/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: showroom cleaning

Description:

Cleaning showroom by market cleaners → 50

Approved
&

Received By

31/05/16

Total → 50

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

Date: 31/05/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Office rent

Description:

Paying office rent → 10,000₹

Approved
&
Received By
[Signature]
31/05/16

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4 Legal authorization and signing

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The author has contribution in conceptualization, visualization, resource, self-supervision, funding acquisition, project administration, research communications, research commercialization, planning and prediction, analysis, writing the original draft, manuscript editing, and publication process. The scholarship or funder has no scholarly role of the design of research, research idea or visualization, research and innovation, drafting of manuscript, editing of manuscript, and publication of manuscript.

6 Declaration of conflicting interests

The author declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

7 Funding

The author received no financial support for the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

8 Data availability

All data generated during the coalescing of this article are included, attached and briefly cited in reference list.

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letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. . 2023, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8315574>.

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 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing &
 process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)^{4*}
 Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission);
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur,
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
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 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
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 Vijellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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111. Hossain, M.A., *Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform*, R.U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com), Editor. 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>.

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 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵
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 Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
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 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
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 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
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- and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs. 2024: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>.
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 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing &
 process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
 Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission);
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur,
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
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 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India: Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

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